

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 5.1

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

Report on mapped needs and the key end-users of the capacity building programme

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List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
CBP	Capacity Building Programme
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
INRAE	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food & Environment
ILVO	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries & Food
LL	Living Lab
NCP	National Contact Point
OIA	Open innovation arrangement
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCAR	Standing Committee on Agroecology Research
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

Amplifying agroecology in Europe via a network of open innovation arrangements (OIAs), more specifically existing out of living labs (LLs) and research infrastructures (RIs) is a complex challenge with multiple facets to be considered including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources and degradation of soil and water quality. But also, supporting the development of necessary competencies needed from all different stakeholders (e.g., researchers, farmers, policy makers, intermediaries, etc.) to make this transition possible. We define a competency as a combination of skills, knowledge, and personal characteristics (attitudes traits, self-concept, etc.).

Tackling this complex challenge requires a thorough identification of the different skills and competencies needed and a capacity building program (CBP) to support different stakeholders within the European agroecology ecosystem.

The first two deliverables of this work package *WP5 Capacity Building* are strongly interlinked with each other.

Therefore, *D5.2 Skills and competencies framework* will focus on categories and specifications of core skills and competencies for accelerating agroecological transition through the development of place-based open innovations and their European networking. Providing the necessary insights to scope a CBP that supports the different key end-users.

This deliverable *D5.1 Report on mapped needs and the key end users of the capacity building programme* (in link with WP2 and WP3) describes the work carried out under task *T5.1 Scoping the capacity building programme*, focusing on providing a framework for capacity building via the identification of key end users and their needs. It describes the necessary building blocks of a CBP and provides suggestions for possible formats (capacity building items) to support the key end-users to gain the necessary competencies.

As a first step the **meaning of capacity building was further refined** (see 2.3.1) to create common understanding within the context of ALL-Ready about what capacity building is and which levels it should comprise. Based on this refined definition, WP5 partners worked on the scoping of the **concepts, topics and criteria** (see 2.3.2), defining a 3-layered approach towards the capacity building programme:

- Transition to agroecology in general
- Setting up and managing Agroecology Living Labs & Research infrastructures
- Setting up a network of Agroecology Living Labs & Research Infrastructures

These previous steps led to **a first preliminary scoping** on what should be part of the CBP (see. 2.3.3) via a holistic approach in which individual feedback from all WP5 partners for every of the 3 identified levels was collected. These inputs were consolidated during multiple bi-weekly work package meetings until consensus was found on this internal draft of the CBP.

This draft was then used to **iterate the framework** together with other work packages from ALL-Ready, but also within the meetings of the SCAR-AE Task Force 3 (capacity building). In this step of the scoping process, also the **main groups of key end-users were identified**: research community, farmers, policy makers, and intermediaries

The outcome of this scoping process, **an exhaustive framework** (see 2.3.4), was then translated into **a more concise overview of formats** (capacity building items) to be validated by multiple groups of key end-users (see 2.3.4).

To **validate this scoped framework**, it was presented to 3 external groups of key end-users (see 2.3.5) before a final internal interaction took place during the ALL-Ready consortium meeting in March 2022.

First an interactive workshop on capacity building was organised with the **external advisory board of ALL-ready** (see 2.3.5.1). After this, the iterated framework was discussed in another interactive workshop (in collaboration with WP4) during the **kick-off meeting of the pilot network of WP3** (see 2.3.5.2).

The last external validation took place via a focused survey addressing the group of **policy and/or decision makers** in which their opinions about the possible formats (capacity building items) was collected (see 2.3.5.3).

Finally, all collected feedback & the CBP was internally discussed during two more interactive workshops with ALL-Ready partners (see 2.3.5.4)

Taking this holistic approach allowed to finalize as a main result **the scoping of a CBP which covers the three levels** as mentioned here above, while providing **a list of validated possible formats** (see 2.3.6) to be prototyped and experimented with within *Task 5.2 Prototyping and experimenting the capacity building programme* in close collaboration with the pilot network of WP3. The results of this task 5.2 will support *Task 5.3 Implementing the capacity building training programme*.

However, since the scoping process made clear that the further development of the CBP will require to maintain a holistic and iterative approach, this deliverable needs to be interpreted as a living document, it will be updated each year, until the end of the project. The 2nd version will be complemented with the prototyping exercises done in task 5.2 and the last version will be finalized after the implementation of the prototyped items in task 5.3.

2. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

This will be done through a participatory approach, among other activities via the pilot network, involving end users and other stakeholders, and considering the factors that favor the development and upscaling of agroecological practices and those that will promote “buy in” for participating in the future network *AgroEcoLLNet*.

ALL-Ready will pave the way for the transition to agroecology in Europe by developing the necessary tools and activities, experimented with the pilot network, that will contribute to the building of the future network.

This deliverable is part of *WP5 Capacity Building* and more specifically of *Task 5.1 Scoping the Capacity building programme*

The goal of this deliverable is to highlight who the key end users are and what the building blocks of the CBP will be (for instance knowledge and skills to implement participatory methodologies and agroecological practices) and give suggestions on how to deliver these building blocks (e.g., key expert training, study visits, workshops).

Chapter 3 describes the rationale behind this deliverable and the approach which was taken to scope the needs of key end users, the building blocks of the CBP, and the suggestions on how to deliver these building blocks. Chapter 4 provides insights about the mapping done in every step of the process. Chapter 5 contains the main conclusions and the next steps based on this deliverable.

This deliverable is **based on the work done in the following other deliverables** of the ALL-Ready project:

- D1.1 Reference document with key concept
- D1.2 Definitions and a set of inclusion criteria for Agroecology living labs, pertinent research infrastructures and their synergies.
- D2.3 Report on drivers of Agroecology transition
- D2.4 Overview of agroecology LLs and RIs in Europe
- D3.1 Stakeholder engagement plan

This deliverable is **closely interdependent with Deliverable *D5.2 Skills and competencies framework*** since the scoping of the building blocks of the CBP and the suggestions on possible formats (capacity building items) are starting from the competencies important for agroecological transition and supporting innovation on agroecology through the connection of LLs and RIs.

3. Rationale and Approach

3.1 Rationale

The overall objective of work package 5 is to prepare and initiate a CBP within the ALL-Ready project as support action for the future European network of Agroecology LLs & RIs.

This CBP will support the further development of, and exchange between existing and new living labs and research infrastructures in agroecology across Europe. Rolling out the CBP will support the transition of European agri-food systems to agroecology by promoting agroecology and LL approaches in RIs and supporting the implementation of principles of LLs within the initiatives of ALL-Ready (pilot network & future partnership).

The CBP will be tailored to the need of the key end users. The key end users will be defined within WP2 where the existing initiatives of LL and RI in the domain of agroecology will be mapped. In addition, the CBP will support the development of ALL-Ready in line with the vision document developed in WP1. The CBP will be prototyped, validated within the pilot network in WP3 and inform the implementation of a European Network of AE LLs & RIs developed in WP4.

Finally, the validated outcomes will define the final materials to be included in (online) learning materials and recorded webinars.

The vision and the mission of the network to be developed, is described in deliverable D1.1. It defines the main requirements for agroecology transition from the socio-economic to environmental context and describes how LLs and RIs are specifically suited to achieve this transition:

Living labs, by definition, produce three categories of values: business, knowledge and social (Dubé et al., 2014), "knowledge" meaning that LLs promote co-learning among the stakeholders and partners engaged. In this way, they serve to support organisational and social transformations.

Place-based LLs, whether they are related to urban or rural development or agroecosystems, additionally aim to improve sustainability and resilience of the socio-ecosystem to which they apply.

LLs for AE transition will work towards improving sustainability and resilience not only at the agroecosystem level, but also at landscape level and considering the food system as a whole.

Research Infrastructures are facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation. They can be used beyond research e.g., for education or public services and they may be single-sited, distributed, or virtual. RIs can be facilities for agroecology transition. They are dedicated to research communities and allow scientists to observe/experiment/predict agroecosystem and agri-food redesign. RIs for agroecology transition are diverse: RIs on national or European roadmaps; systemic and innovative experiments; modelling/multicriteria assessment (life cycle analysis tools); eInfrastructure that provide data, metadata, and services

D1.1 served as starting point for the scoping of the needed CBP, including the concepts, topics and criteria needed to support every level of the framework.

The work performed in this deliverable is linked with the work done in:

- WP1 - Vision and mission of the network
- WP2 – Mapping, analysis and overview of existing mechanisms for carrying out participatory agroecological research and innovation including KPIs for the network
- WP3 – Coordination of stakeholder engagement and the ALL-Ready pilot

- WP4 – Implementation and sustainability of the network

Furthermore, this deliverable took advantage of the already existing capacity building expertise from ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs), among others, like:

The general **capacity building programme**¹ of ENoLL consisting of tailor-made offers constructed in collaboration with organisations, individuals and companies aspiring to develop a successful living lab. The program is built on elements of living lab trainings, mentoring and additional targeted learning materials. In the Capacity Building Programme of ENoLL the learning is customised to cases, thematics and domains specifically.

Available **knowledge materials** like factsheets, best practices, toolkits, webinars, podcasts, publications, e-courses, etc. Experiences from other projects from ENoLL, including capacity building in developed living lab methodologies:

- [https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/ull_handbook_online_version_\(page_43-48\)](https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/ull_handbook_online_version_(page_43-48))
- [https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/iscape_guidebook_digital_\(page_79-80,_page_124-129\)](https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/iscape_guidebook_digital_(page_79-80,_page_124-129))
- [http://organicity.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Organicity-Playbook_2018-1.pdf_\(page_28-29\)](http://organicity.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Organicity-Playbook_2018-1.pdf_(page_28-29))

Inputs were gathered from the WP5 partners, other WP leaders and the SCAR-AE Task Force 3 to guarantee the work done in ALL-Ready to be aligned with the other running CSA (AE4EU) and the overall approach towards Horizon Europe on this matter.

Partners from WP5 participated in the organised activities of the SCAR-AE Task force 3 on capacity building.

Later, it was validated by the key end-users of the framework during multiple validation activities (e.g., workshop, survey) with different stakeholders of the different levels (EU-level- Living Lab Level – local level). Furthermore, also feedback from our External Advisory Board was collected.

3.2 Approach

The mapping of the needs of the key end users and the scoping of a CBP within ALL Ready, also making suggestions on how to deliver the capacity building, was **structured in 6 steps**:

Step 1: The **meaning of capacity building** in the context of ALL-ready was refined (see 4.1) to specify the skills and knowledge needed.

Step 2: After this, a **preliminary scoping of the agroecological concepts, topics and criteria** took place to define the skills and knowledge needed for every 'level' of the framework (see 4.2)

- Transition to agroecology in general
- Setting up and managing Agroecology Living Labs & Research infrastructures
- Setting up a network of Living Labs & Research Infrastructures

Step 3: These exercises lead to a **first compilation of an internal scoping** within the project consortium of the CBP for ALL-Ready (see. 4.3)

Step 4: A **refinement of the skills and knowledge needed** for each of the identified groups of key end-users was discussed within WP5 to create a **preliminary overview of**

¹ https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/learninglab_brochure

capacity building instruments which could be used to develop and strengthen these skills and competencies to generate a sustainable transformation from within (see 4.4)

Step 5: Following this, multiple validation exercises took place, based on these different inputs:

- A validation workshop was organised with the external advisory board of the ALL Ready project (see 4.5.1)
- A validation workshop with different **key end-users of the pilot network (WP3)** was organised to validate the draft framework and to further refine the CBP (see 4.5.2)
- A survey addressed to the group of policy and/or decision makers to collect their feedback to further scope the CBP for **policy makers and/or decision makers** as well (see 4.5.3)
- A final internal workshop was organised with all the partners from the project during the consortium meeting (see 4.5.4)

Step 6: All these actions leading to **the Capacity building framework** and a list of suggestions on formats (capacity building items) on how to deliver it (*see 4.6*)

This CBP will be:

- Further prototyped and co-designed within Task 5.2 Prototyping and experimenting the capacity building training programme (M12-M24)
- Getting implemented in Task 5.3 Implementing the capacity building training Programme (M24-M36)
- Scaled-up in Task 5.4 Scale-up of the capacity building training programme: communication and dissemination activities (M12-M36)

4. Scoping the capacity building programme and the needs of key end-users

4.1 Capacity Building: refining the meaning

Within *subtask 5.1.1 Specification of skills, competencies, and knowledge for key end-users*, the team of WP5 worked in parallel on refining the meaning of Capacity building together with the work on defining competencies within the ALL-Ready framework in *Deliverable 5.2 Skills and competencies framework*, discussing the crucial elements needed for scoping a CBP to enhance agroecology transition. They started with creating common understanding within ALL-Ready about what capacity building is and which levels of capacity building should be tackled.

According to United Nations², Capacity-building is defined as the "process of **developing and strengthening** the skills, instincts, abilities, processes and resources that organisations and communities need to survive, adapt, and thrive in a fast-changing world." An essential ingredient in capacity-building is **transformation that is generated and sustained over time from within**; transformation of this kind goes beyond performing tasks to changing mindsets and attitudes

² <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/capacity-building>

The concept of capacity building has traditionally been highly linked to development cooperation. Already in the early seventies international organisations (e.g. UNDP) have been enhancing capacity building via (technical) skills training, mostly in rural areas and in administrative sectors of developing countries.

According to the definition of United Nations Development Programme (UNDP³): "In the global context, capacity refers to the ability of individuals and institutions **to make and implement decisions and perform functions** in an effective, efficient, and sustainable manner.

Following Lear⁴ (Laboratory of Economics, Antitrust and Regulation), thinking of capacity building as simply training or human resource development might be insufficient.

Looking at it from **a 3-level perspective provides a more holistic approach to empower the essential ingredient of transformation generated and sustained over time from within:**

- At the **individual level**, capacity building refers to the process of changing individual attitudes and behaviours by improving individual skills, knowledge and performance through training, experiences, motivations, and incentives, while maximizing the benefits of participation, knowledge exchange and ownership.
- At the **institutional level**, it focuses on improving organisational performance through strategies, plans, rules and regulations, partnerships, leadership, organisational politics, and power structures, and strengthening organisational systems, processes, and roles and responsibilities.
- At the **systemic level**, it emphasises the improvement of the policy framework to address economic, political, environmental, and social factors, including economic growth, financing, labour markets, political context, policy and legislative environment, class structures, and cultural aspects in a coherent and mutually reinforcing fashion.

Furthermore, LEAR indicates that specific and targeted formats (capacity building items) need to be developed at each single level, providing suggestions for possible formats:

- At the individual level:
 - Training programs
 - Business development activities
 - Workshops for in-depth discussion of specific topics
 - Conferences
- At the institutional level:
 - Development of internal policies
 - Organisational and procedural restructuring
- At the systemic level:
 - Advocacy initiatives
 - Consultations
 - Open dialogue
 - Reforms

³ <https://unsdg.un.org/sites/default/files/UNDG-UNDAF-Companion-Pieces-8-Capacity-Development.pdf>

⁴ <https://www.learlab.com/insights/capacity-building-is-it-only-a-matter-of-training/>

4.2 Capacity Building: concepts, topics, and criteria

4.2.1 Actions

A smaller task force within WP5 existing of representatives from INRAE, ILVO and ENOLL worked on **scoping the criteria for capacity building in ALL-Ready**.

They considered the Individual, Institutional and Systemic level as indicated by LEAR and combined it with the work from WP1 on **concepts within Task 1.1** *Comparison of strategic visions on agroecology and the role of place-based open innovation processes in achieving the transition*

Figure 1: Approach of Task 1.1

SOCIAL CONTEXT

FIELD

Figure 2: AE transition indicators

Next to this they looked at the work done on **topics** within *Task 1.2: Propose and agree on the defining features (indicators) of agroecology living labs and agroecology research infrastructures, and inclusion criteria for the components of the ALL-Ready network.*

Figure 3: Task 1.2 What will this network look like?

The work done in that Task 1.2 already collected valuable information about key elements around Agroecology in general and Agroecology transition, among others from the FAO⁵ (Food and Agriculture Organisation), and HLPE⁶ (High level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition)

As explained in *Deliverable 5.2 - Skills and competencies framework*, the need for approaching this in three levels became clear since the actions and performance of the key end users of each of the three levels seem to be different.

4.2.2 Results

The smaller task force within WP5, combining all these inputs with the main objectives of the ALL-Ready project, **collected the criteria for the ALL-Ready project within three levels**, making **criteria suggestions for every of the three levels**:

- Agroecology transition in general
- Agroecological living labs, research and open innovation initiatives.
- A European network of agroecological living labs & research infrastructures

Agroecology transition in general	<p>Fundamental pillars (Fairness, diversity, etc.)</p> <p>AE Transition indicators (Culture, co-creation, resilience, efficiency, etc.)</p> <p>Activities for AE transition (work with farmers, agri-food systems adjusted to local, etc.)</p> <p>Orientations of AE transition (increase efficiency, re-establish a direct connection with consumers, etc.)</p>
Living Labs & research infrastructures in agroecology	<p>For Living Labs (ENoLL's evaluation criteria set as a basis):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation, management & governance of the living lab • Experience in living lab operations • Interest & ability to participate in regional or (inter)national innovation system mechanisms • An iterative living lab process & real-life setting • Users & people engagement approach • Quality of methods & tools • Roles & responsibilities of qualified staff • Access & availability of equipment & infrastructure • Internal & external communication • Openness of innovation processes & partnerships • Feedback protection & author's rights • Co-created values for all involved stakeholders • Coverage of the value chain • Business Model & access & ability to funding • SWOT & strategic plans for the future <p>For research infrastructures (work done in WP1 as a basis):</p>

⁵ FAO 2018, *The 10 elements of agroecology. Guiding the transition to sustainable food and agricultural systems*, Rome

⁶ HLPE 2019, *Agroecological and other innovative approaches for sustainable agriculture and food systems that enhance food security and nutrition*, Rome

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroecology transition criteria • Maturity agroecology research infrastructure criteria • Pertinence agroecology research infrastructure criteria • Networking criteria
A network of living labs and research infrastructures in agroecology	<p>Criteria dimensions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Actors (admin, LLs, RIs, facilitating organisations) 2. Openness & interpretation in the real world 3. The goals, aims, actions of the network 4. Capacity & resources 5. The essential features of the network 6. Set of roles within the innovation network 7. Competencies of the innovation advisors 8. Responsibilities and requirements 9. Policy implications

By doing so, they provided the starting point for the first internal 1st draft of the CBP.

4.3 Capacity Building: internal 1st draft capacity building topics

4.3.1 Actions

Following the collection of the concepts, topics and criteria which are essential for the CBP (see 4.2), a **first internal draft of the capacity building topics** was **co-created by all partners of WP5**, focusing on the three levels.

The aim of this step was to **identify what should be included in the capacity building programme** within the three identified levels.

To do so, all partners of WP5 provided feedback and suggestions for capacity building topics for each of the three levels individually first from their different expertise and backgrounds (research-, practitioners-, living lab-, policy- and/or network management-oriented) as organisations. This individual feedback was then discussed during multiple (bi-weekly) WP5 meetings to align it further with the earlier collected criteria (see 4.2).

4.3.2 Results

In the overview here below, we list up the most important topics, linking it to the criteria suggestions from the previous step (see 4.2), but also with the parts of Deliverable 5.2 (Skills and competencies framework) to this regard.

Looking at the level of agroecology in general the most important topics to include are:

- Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition :
Step 4.2: fundamental pillars
Deliverable 5.2: Towards a shared understanding of agroecology and its potential in transition of farming and food systems
- Drivers and barriers:
Step 4.2: AE transition indicators
Deliverable 5.2: How to accelerate agroecology innovation in the transition of farm and food systems

- Best practices:
 - Step 4.2: Activities for AE transition*
 - Deliverable 5.2: Towards a shared understanding of agroecology and its potential in transition of farming and food systems*
- A systemic view to agroecology (orientations of AE transition)
 - Step 4.2: Orientations of AE transition*
 - Deliverable 5.2: Grasping the needs for agroecology transition to more sustainable farming and food systems*

Looking at the level of LLs & RIs in agroecology the most important topics to include are:

- How to set up and run an agroecology LL and/or RI
 - ENoLL's evaluation criteria as a basis*
 - Pertinence, maturity & networking criteria for RIs*
- Roles of LLs & RIs
 - ENoLL's evaluation criteria as a basis*
 - Pertinence criteria for RIs*
- Impact of LLs & RIs
 - ENoLL's evaluation criteria as a basis*
 - Maturity criteria for RIs*
- Multi-actor cooperation and communication (Networking criteria)
 - ENoLL's evaluation criteria as a basis*
 - Networking criteria for RIs*

Looking at the level of a network of LLs & RIs the most important topics are:

- Guidelines and roadmaps for policy makers
 - Goals, aims & actions of the network/ policy implications/essential features/ competencies of innovation advisors/ responsibilities and requirements/ capacity & resources*
- How to link LLs and RIs
 - Actors/set of roles/openness & interpretation*

The full overview of the outcome of this step can be found in **Annex 1** of this deliverable.

4.4 Capacity Building: What for whom

4.4.1 Actions

Before finetuning the CBP, during this next step the framework was further iterated and even more expanded based on the input from other ALL-Ready project partners, but also based on the input from the SCAR-AE Task force 3 on capacity building. The SCAR-AE is preparing the future partnership.

This SCAR task force included members from the ALL-Ready project in general and WP5 more specific, together with members from the CSA project AE4EU and under supervision of colleagues of DG Agri.

The aim of this SCAR-AE task force was to:

- formulate recommendations on research and innovation instruments needed to test agroecology concepts and practices.
- identify bottlenecks

- suggest instruments and capacity building to boost agroecology in relation to the following key end-users:
 - research community
 - farmers
 - advisors
 - overall value chain (including consumers)
 - policy
 - communication

This SCAR-AE task force on Capacity building organised 7 meetings between April and June 2021 to reach consensus on identified bottlenecks and barriers, proposed instruments/infrastructures and capacity building activities (e.g. training, demonstration, education...).

4.4.2 Results

Based on the work done in these SCAR-AE task force meetings, within WP5 the main groups of key end-users of the ALL-Ready CBP were implemented as follows:

- Research community
- Policy makers
- Farmers
- Consumers
- Intermediaries & value chain actors (e.g. advisors, living lab managers ...)
- Communication

Following this a matching took place between the input of the SCAR-AE task force and the previous inputs from WP5 partners (see 4.3) for each of the three levels

- **Transition in agroecology**

Target audience CB for whom?)	SCAR (questions to tackle/ goals)	WP5 (questions to tackle/ goals based on WP5 matrix)
Research	Long-term data series on agroecosystems Agroecological management practices Studies on the social and environmental impact of agroecological schemes Standardized agroecological model for scientific and educational purposes Local knowledge Methodological approach of agroecological research	Conceptualization of transition to agroecology (resilience, robustness, vulnerability) Data collections and sharing Transversal management Social and economic particularities Common understanding of the scope and diversity of agroecological transitions including barriers / drivers, benefits, and the roles of different types of actors. Understanding long-term implications and benefits of such transitions. Clarifying the relationship between agroecological transitions and organic farming

Farmers	Attractiveness of rural lifestyle Shift from conventional farming Special attention to aging issue Knowledge intensity and availability of that knowledge to farmers and advisers	Valorization of agroecological practices and of biodiversity services Connection between the farmer and the consumer, the farmer, and the citizen Agronomic and practice, technology-related particularities
Consumers	Awareness of the costs and added value of agroecological practices	
Policy (facilitators, advisors, policy-makers)	Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries Long-term, strategic system-thinking and planning in agroecological practice Precise indicators that quantify the magnitude and quality of the ecosystem services	Develop systems and holistic analysis Innovation tracking and demonstrations
Communication (tools/ infrastructure/ actions)	A specific mechanism to ensure the sharing of experiences and best practices across Member States on the adoption of agroecological approaches	

- **AE LLS and RIs**

Target audience for whom?	SCAR (questions to tackle/ goals)	WP5 (questions to tackle/ goals based on WP5 matrix)
Research	Research laboratories on scientific, technical, and socio-cultural and economic agroecological issues	How to value common goods How to do with imposed time scales (seasonal experimentations) and with long term transformation/impact on future generations Dealing with very different and heterogeneous knowledge (practice and theory, tacit and explicit) Implication of researchers and academia, at which level and for what role - Role and expectations from the local/territory CB on multi-actor communication and cooperation Integrating ecological / environmental priorities with economic / socio-economic priorities - creating and understanding common objectives.

Farmers	Boosting high-tech farming (precision farming, remote control, digital machinery etc.) Digital and computer models for farmers including blockchain technologies	
Consumers	Research groups for Europe-wide strategies to promote benefits of agroecological schemes to consumers	How to promote agroecology and LL approaches inside RI's Data sharing & collection
Policy (facilitators, advisors, policy-makers)	Pressure on farmers and smallholdings to intensify agricultural practices Facilitators, advisors etc. know how to communicate but lack skills/knowledge on agroecology	Models of meta-governance (large diversity of stakeholders) Business models of AE LL and RI Competencies and skills (guideline) on how to build, operate (economic viability) and further innovate within AE LLs and RIs of different levels, maturity, and geographic scope Importance of long-term business models How to set up and run AE LL
Communication (tools/ infrastructure/ actions)	Long term platforms (multiple actors) A European newsletters service on funding calls and any help for the agroecology sector	Identify main limits and levers to data management, PI, multi-users involvements Guidance on how to utilize and combine the range of funding opportunities

- **A European network of AE LLs & RIs**

Target audience for CB (for whom?)	SCAR (questions to tackle/ goals)	WP5 (questions to tackle/ goals based on WP5 matrix)
Research	Living lab covering diversity of territories and diversity of actors within LL. Meta-analyses System thinking as neutral entry point Banks/repositories of ancient/traditional and minor/forgotten seeds and varieties	Capacity to identify and raise new research questions in the run of LL and RI and to extract the generic value of local advances
Farmers	Digital and computer models for farmers including blockchain technologies	Tool to facilitate the exchange of best practices at EU level on Agroecology, LL and RI, and the institutional setting to it related

	<p>Access to agroecological farm and food system demonstration networks</p> <p>Production of a collection of agroecological farmers stories and testimonies</p>	<p>ALL-Ready website / Knowledge Hub</p> <p>ALL-Ready test network</p>
Consumers	<p>Establish research groups for Europe-wide strategies to promote benefits of agroecological schemes to consumers</p> <p>Platform containing educational products related to capacity building of consumers</p>	
Policy (facilitators, advisors, policy-makers)	<p>Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE)</p> <p>A permanent discussion forum among all policy makers (local-regional- national)</p> <p>Skills/knowledge development</p>	<p>To train and support in building the foundation of cooperation among network members (skills needed, capacity needed etc.) and in maintaining this cooperation (clear interest specification)</p> <p>Capacity and step-by-step guidance to set up, manage and monitor a network and understanding and assessing its long-term sustainability. Guidance for funders and policy stakeholders</p> <p>A roadbook for decision makers/officials to set up a network of AL</p> <p>A guide for policy-makers for understanding all the funding schemes that can support LLs</p> <p>A guide to facilitate national multi-actor dialogues between national policy-makers and all stakeholders with a stake on Agroecology, LL and RI</p>
Communication (tools/ infrastructure/ actions)	<p>Living labs/agroecological office</p> <p>Online platform where all publications, resources and forums on agroecology are concentrated</p> <p>Practical online tool for multi actors</p> <p>Create a new magazine?</p>	<p>ALL-Ready website / Knowledge Hub</p> <p>Guidelines for funders Platforms and events for sharing experiences and competencies</p> <p>Tool to facilitate the exchange of best practices at EU level on Agroecology, LL and RI</p>

These matching tables were then transposed into one overall overview during the regular bi-weekly WP5 meetings, to list up all the inputs collected and to further enrich the inputs as given by ENoLL as a WP5 lead.

Stakeholder groups	Research			Farmers			Policy makers		
	Input SCAR	Input WP5	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Input WP5	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Input WP5	Possible CB items
Agro-Ecology in general	standardized agroecological model for scientific and educational purposes	Conceptualization of transition to agroecology (resilience, robustness, vulnerability)	Standardized agroecological model	Shift from conventional farming	Valorization of agroecological practices & biodiversity services		Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries		Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries
	methodological approach of agroecological research	Common understanding of the scope and diversity of agroecological transitions including barriers / drivers, benefits and the roles of different types of actors,	Training courses on environmental communication techniques to make agroecology attractive for farmers & consumers	Attractiveness of rural lifestyle & farming	Agronomic and practice	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Long-term, strategic system thinking and planning in agroecological practice	develop systems and holistic analysis	Strategic system thinking agroecological model
	long-term data series on agroecosystems + digital and computer models for monitoring	Data collections and sharing	Open databank?	Special attention to aging issue			guides on funding resources to support AE transition in farms		Guidelines on funding resources
	studies on the social and environmental impact of agroecological schemes	social and economic particularities	A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts	Knowledge intensity & availability of knowledge to the farmers		A knowledge catalogue:	precise indicators that quantify the magnitude & quality of the ecosystem services	innovation tracking and demonstration	KPI's for measuring impacts
	local knowledge & scattered information	Transversal management		Lack of education, training, skills on AE	Connection between the farmer & the consumer + the farmer & the citizen	Training on agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances (e.g. "A gro(w) to Z")	Inconsistent, fragmented and uneven structures/mechanisms at the national and European levels to facilitate the co-creation of innovative solutions		Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology
	agroecological management practices	Understanding long-term implications and benefits of such transitions. Clarifying the relationship between agroecological transitions and organic farming		Labour intensity: AE is more labour intensive, harder to mechanise. Productivity related barriers. Perception of low profitability of production through AE	Technology related particularities		trade-off between local empowerment and national commitments		
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-ecology		Role and expectations from the local territory	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits	Digital and computer models for farmers including blockchain technologies		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	pressure on farmers & smallholdings to intensify agricultural practices		Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits
	Research laboratories on scientific, technical and socio-cultural and economic agroecological issues	Dealing with very different and heterogeneous knowledge (practice and theory, tacit and explicit)	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")		particularities for ALL		skills & knowledge on agroecology	How to set up and run an ALL	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")
		how to value common goods - How to do with imposed time scales (seasonal experimentations) and with long term			functioning of LL and their set-up		Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")	meta-governance models (large diversity of stakeholders)	A knowledge catalogue: skills, governance models, business models
		Implication of researchers and academia, at which level and for what role	A knowledge catalogue: roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation, best practices, demonstration videos, limits & levers		Multi-actor communication and cooperation			business models of AE LL and RI	
		Integrating ecological / environmental priorities with economic / socio-economic priorities - creating and understanding common objectives			competencies & skills needed			competencies & skills (guidelines) on how to build, operate & further innovate within AE LL and RIs of different levels, maturity & geographic scope	Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills
		create model regions where demonstration on AE can be made + boosting high tec farming for AE	multi-actor communication & cooperation	Promotion events about ALL's & RIs	Boosting high-tech farming (precision farming, remote control, digital machinery etc.)		Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies		
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Living lab covering diversity of territories (across labs) and diversity of actors within LL		Mapping of ALL's & RIs	Digital and computer models for farmers including blockchain technologies	ALL-ready-website/knowledge hub	A knowledge catalogue: barriers & benefits of networked approach, economical & societal impacts, funding	Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE)	Capacity and step-by-step guidance to set up, manage and monitor a network and understanding and assessing its long-term sustainability. Guidance for funders and policy stakeholders	KPI's for measuring impacts
	Meta-analyses	Capacity to identify and raise new research questions in the run of LL and RI and to extract the generic value of local advances	Open databank?	Access to agroecological farm and food system demonstration networks	ALL-ready test network	A (European) community platform	Skills & knowledge development	to train and support in building the foundation of cooperation among network members (skills needed, capacity needed etc.) and in maintaining this cooperation (clear interest specification)	Guidelines/roadbook/ training around the set up of a network of ALL, facilitate multi-actor dialogues, understand needed funding schemes
	Banks/repositories of ancient/traditional and minor/forgotten seeds and varieties			Production of a collection of agroecological farmers stories and testimonies	Tool to facilitate the exchange of best practices at EU level on Agroecology, LL and RI, and the institutional setting to it related	Demonstration videos to show the benefits of being part of a local/regional (international) network of ALL's	A permanent discussion forum among all policy makers (local/regional) (international)	A roadbook for decision makers/officials to set up a network of ALL	
	System thinking as neutral entry point + research strategies on AE management practices		A strategic system thinking research agenda about ALL's				Living labs/agroecological office	a guide for policy-makers for understanding all the funding schemes that can support LLs 2)a guide to facilitate national multi-actor dialogues between national policy-makers and all stakeholders with a stake on Agroecology, LL and RI	Living labs/ agroecological office

Figure 5 Overview of capacity building items what for whom

Input SCAR	Consumers			Intermediaries (advisors/ running managing Living labs included) & value chain actors			Communication (tools/infrastructures/actions)	
	Input WP5	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Input WP5	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Possible CB items	
Awareness of the costs and added value of agroecological practices			Incoherence between supporting & hampering transition policies			a specific mechanism to ensure the sharing of experiences and best practices across Member States on the adoption of agroecological approaches	A (European) community platform on agroecology (e.g. The facebook for farmers)	
realistic expectations in terms of seasonality and types of products you can find		Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Influence of mainstream farmer organisations on policy processes (lack of support for AE)		Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	target urban/territorial food movements with communications about AE		
Affordability of AE products for some groups			retail logistics have been adapted to industrial-scale farming and smaller-scale cannot match			communication between cities/neighborhoods + between rural areas		
challenge to change diets towards 'sustainable diets'			paradox: long chains may be cheaper to operate than short ones			communication between different actors (consumers, research, value chain actors, farmers)		
difficult logistics access (food deserts where you can only access mainstream food) - less selling points			Lack of skills and knowledge on AE		A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts	local knowledge & scattered information		
			knowledge on how to process AE products (variety or plant mixes)				A knowledge catalogue:	
research groups for Europe-wide strategies to promote benefits of agroecological schemes to consumers	How to promote agroecology and LL approaches inside Rf's	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits	Support peer learning and co-learning processes/approaches	multi-actor communication & cooperation	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")	long term platforms	A (European) community platform	
	Data sharing & collection	Open databank?	technologies to process AE products		A knowledge catalogue: technologies	a European newsletters service on funding calls and any help for the agroecology sector	Transparent way of funding calls & opportunities	
			technologies to manage more farms/chains					
Platform containing educational products related to capacity building of consumers	ALL-ready-website/knowledge hub	A knowledge catalogue	Support peer learning and co-learning processes/approaches		A (European) community platform	Online platform where all publications, resources and forums on agroecology are concentrated	A knowledge catalogue	
	ALL-ready test network		Absence of a specific mechanism to ensure the sharing of experiences			Practical online tool for multi actors	A (European) community platform	
Establish research groups for Europe-wide strategies to promote benefits of agroecological schemes to consumers	Tool to facilitate the exchange of best practices at EU level on Agroecology, LL and RI, and the institutional setting to it related	A (European) community platform	Localised/regional knowledge: how to share it?	Developing several local "hubs" rather than centralized forms which can be localized, "small" centers for sharing knowledge (small distances, similar local characteristics). But the connections between several hubs within a	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Create a new magazine?	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	
	DLLD21	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Common languages, strategies & communication between different actors					

Figure 5 bis Overview of capacity building items what for whom

The grey fields indicate that for that group of key end-users no immediate capacity building item (format) was suggested, nor by the SCAR-Ae task force 3, nor by the WP5 partners.

A more detailed view of this outcome can also be found as **Annex 2** of this deliverable.

During the last step of the scoping process, the overlapping capacity building items returning for multiple groups of key end-users were merged and translated into **a more concise overview of formats (capacity building items) to be developed** for the different identified groups of key end-users.

	Research	Policy	Farmers	Consumers	Intermediaries (advisors/ running managing Living labs included) & value chain actors	Communication (tools/infrastructures/actio ns)
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Mapping of ALL's & RI's	KPI's for measuring impacts	A (European) community platform			
	Open databank?	Guidelines/ roadbook/ training around the set up of a network of ALL, facilitate multi-actor dialogues, understand needed funding schemes	A knowledge catalogue: barriers & benefits of networked approach, economical & societal impacts, funding			
	A strategic system thinking research agenda about ALL's	Living labs/ agroecological office	Demonstration videos to show the benefits of being part of a local/regional/ (inter)national network of ALL's	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology		
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-ecology	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		
	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")					
	A knowledge catalogue: roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation, best practices, demonstration videos, limits & levers	A knowledge catalogue: skills, governance models, business models			A knowledge catalogue: technologies	Transparent way of funding calls & opportunities
	Promotion events about ALL's & RI's	Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills	Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	Open databank?		A (European) community platform
Agro-Ecology in general	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology					A (European) community platform on agroecology (e.g. The facebook for farmers)
	Standardized system thinking agroecological model		Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries			
	Training courses on environmental communication techniques to make agroecology attractive for farmers & consumers	Guidelines on funding resources	Training on agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances (e.g. "A gro(w) to Z")			
	Open databank?	KPI's for measuring impacts				
	A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts		A knowledge catalogue:		A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts	A knowledge catalogue:

Figure 6 Concise overview of non-validated formats

The main indicated capacity building items (formats) before the validation process are:

- A knowledge catalogue
- A European community platform
- Different types of training
- Dissemination & promotion events
- Different types of guidelines

A more detailed view of this outcome can also be found as **Annex 3** of this deliverable.

4.5 Capacity Building: Validation of the scoped framework

4.5.1 Actions

During the last step in the process of scoping the capacity building framework, **feedback from multiple important stakeholders was collected** on the validation of the developed framework & capacity building items.

Three different main target groups were addressed in different ways:

- The **External advisory board** of ALL-Ready during their first meeting. This advisory board exists out of representatives of known organisations and bodies in the field of sustainable food systems, such as e.g. Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO)⁷, EU Science Hub - Joint Research Centre⁸, SCAR Food Systems SWG⁹, BiodivERSa ERA-NET¹⁰, BIOEAST¹¹, and WWF¹².
- Members of the **pilot network** during an interactive workshop, included in the Kick Off Meeting of the Pilot Network which took place in December 2021.
- **Policy makers & decision makers** via a short survey which took place in January 2022 with the help of SCAR.

The opinion of researchers got addressed via the regular meetings within the ALL-Ready project.

Finally, an internal discussion with all the ALL-Ready partners took place during the consortium meeting in Paris, March 8th & 9th 2022.

4.5.2 External advisory board

During the first **External advisory board** meeting which took place in October 2021, members of the board were asked 2 questions:

- Do you agree on the 3-level approach presented?
- Agroecology in general
- Living Labs and Research Infrastructures in Agroecology
- Network of living labs & research infrastructures
- From your perspective, did we forget an important group of key end users?

The members of the external advisory board perceived the 3-level approach over all as very positive and be extremely useful, while making the comment about the need for a very clear definition of agroecology and the different ideas and concepts that exist regarding agroecology.

Furthermore, they suggested some additions/adaptations to the defined main target groups:

⁷ <https://www.fao.org/home/en>

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en>

⁹ <https://scar-europe.org/index.php/food>

¹⁰ <https://www.biodiversa.org/>

¹¹ <https://bioeast.eu/>

¹² <https://www.wwf.eu/>

Figure 7 Input from the external advisory board on WP5 Capacity building

Based on their feedback following steps were taken within WP5 to further refine the capacity building framework:

- A new Capacity Building item for all main target groups was added to the overview (see 1.3.4): A **clear definition & description about agroecology** in general compared to other types of farming (e.g. organic farming)
- The main target group of **Value chain actors** got further enriched with a more clear description about who is included
- The main target group of **Consumers was renamed to Citizens** and enriched with a more clear description about who is included to expand this group of key end-users into a more holistic approach
- A differentiation will be made between LLs and Ris

	Research	Policy	Farmers	Citizens (consumers, civil society organizations, NGO's...)	Intermediaries (advisors/running managing Living labs included) & value chain actors (traders, retailers, transport...)	Communication (tools/infrastructures/actions)
Agro-Ecology in general	A clear definition & description about agroecology in general compared to other types of farming (e.g. organic farming)					
	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology					A (European) community platform on agroecology (e.g. The facebook for farmers)
	Standardized system thinking agroecological model		Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries			
	Training courses on environmental communication techniques to make agroecology attractive for farmers & consumers	Guidelines on funding resources	Training on agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances (e.g. "A gro(w) to Z"			
	Open databank?	KPI's for measuring impacts				
A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts		A knowledge catalogue:		A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts	A knowledge catalogue:	
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-ecology	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		
	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")				Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")	
	A knowledge catalogue: roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation, best practices, demonstration videos, limits & levers	A knowledge catalogue: skills, governance models, business models			A knowledge catalogue: technologies	Transparent way of funding calls & opportunities
	Promotion events about ALL's & RI's	Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills	Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	Open databank?		A (European) community platform
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Mapping of ALL's & RI's	KPI's for measuring impacts	A (European) community platform			
	Open databank?	Guidelines/ roadbook/ training around the set up of a network of ALL, facilitate multi-actor dialogues, understand needed funding schemes		A knowledge catalogue: barriers & benefits of networked approach, economical & societal impacts, funding		
	A strategic system thinking research agenda about ALL's	Living labs/ agroecological office	Demonstration videos to show the benefits of being part of a local/regional/ (inter)national network of ALL's	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology		

 newly added after validation EAB

Figure 8 Overview of capacity building items after validation by the external advisory board

A more detailed view of this outcome can also be found as **Annex 4** of this deliverable.

4.5.3 ALL-Ready Pilot Network

During the kick-off meeting with the ALL-Ready **Pilot Network** which took place in December 2021 a joint workshop for WP4 & WP5 was organised to collect their feedback on the **needed competencies** to:

- Foster transition in agroecology in general
- Set up and run an agroecology living lab and/or research infrastructure

Furthermore, the benefits of a network of living labs and research infrastructures were discussed. Next to this **the role of a network to empower these competencies** was investigated.

ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

D5.1 Report on mapped needs and the key end users of the capacity building programme – April 2022

The **members of the pilot network participating** in this workshop were mainly researchers **representing the main target group of Intermediaries** since most of them oversee the running of a living lab and/or research infrastructure. They also provided **feedback for other members of their LLs or RIs** (e.g., farmers) when they could base their insights on for example a survey, a workshop or discussions with these members.

A comprehensive overview¹³ of the needed clusters of competencies for running an agroecology LL or RI, together with important needed competencies for actors in agroecology LL and/or is integrated into deliverable 5.2 which focus on the competencies and skills for key end-users.

In **Annex 5** you find the complete overview of all mentioned competencies.

The last part of the workshop investigated which role a network of living labs and research infrastructures can play in relation to building capacities.

Figure 9 benefits of a European network of LLs & RIs mentioned by the pilot network members

The participants of the pilot network identified two crucial roles which the network can play in this:

- **Developing skills for facilitation and organisation of co-creation sessions**, both at the design level of co-creation as at the level of basic facilitation of events
- **Developing skills and knowledge on how to set up a living lab.** When setting up a LL, and especially an agroecology LL, many challenges need to be dealt with

This knowledge and skills can be developed by offering following formats (capacity building items) here below:

- An **online community platform** to share best practices
- Training sessions and workshops

¹³ ALL-Ready workshop reporting of the first pilot network meeting section 2.2.4: exploring the added value of a future network and competencies for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI

- An **online knowledge hub** of best practices
- 1-2 page guides
- **Simple videos** instead of complicated documents
- Space for organising distributed experiments based on key drivers of change

Finally, they mentioned the **additional other benefits of a network** as to:

- Information exchange at the European level
- Development of suitable funding strategy
- Increasing **robustness of evidence** and potential for **awareness raising of opportunities and benefits of transition** for farmers, consumers and other actors in the value chain
- **Increasing impact and outreach**: potential for a European network to become a key driver of change
- Organisation of **events**

In **Annex 6** you find the complete overview of all feedback around the network as given by the participants.

Following the workshop, the partners of WP5 matched the feedback with the current version of the CBP as it looked like after the feedback of the External Advisory Board (see 1.3.5.1). Adaptations/additions were made to the overview to respond to the feedback of the participants of the workshop:

1. The order of the main target groups was switched to make it visually clearer
2. Knowledge on AE principles was added to the knowledge catalogue in the level of Agroecology in general and was added to the target group of farmers
3. Training on agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances was added to the group of intermediaries
4. Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies was added to the target group of intermediaries
5. Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies was added to the target group of intermediaries
6. Knowledge catalogue on technologies was added to the target group of farmers

	Research	Policy	Intermediaries (advisors/ running managing Living labs included) & value chain actors (traders, retailers, transport,...)	Farmers	Citizens (consumers, civil society organizations, NGO's...)	Communication (tools/infrastructures/act ions)
Agro-Ecology in general	A clear definition & description about agroecology in general compared to other types of farming (e.g. organic farming)					
	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology					A (European) community platform on agroecology (e.g. The facebook for farmers)
	Standardized system thinking agroecological model			Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries		
	Training courses on environmental communication techniques to make agroecology attractive for farmers & consumers	Guidelines on funding resources	Training on agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances (e.g. "A gro(w) to Z"			
	Open databank?	KPI's for measuring impacts				
A knowledge catalogue: AE principles, conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts		A knowledge catalogue: AE principles, conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts			A knowledge catalogue:	
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-ecology	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies		Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits	
	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")					
	A knowledge catalogue: roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation, best practices, demonstration videos, limits & levers	A knowledge catalogue: skills, governance models, business models	A knowledge catalogue: technologies			Transparent way of funding calls & opportunities
	Promotion events about ALL's & RI's	Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills	Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies		Open databank?	A (European) community platform
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Mapping of ALL's & RI's	KPI's for measuring impacts	A (European) community platform			
	Open databank?	Guidelines/ roadbook/ training around the set up of a network of ALL, facilitate multi-actor dialogues, understand needed funding schemes	A knowledge catalogue: barriers & benefits of networked approach, economical & societal impacts, funding			
	A strategic system thinking research agenda about ALL's	Living labs/ agroecological office	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Demonstration videos to show the benefits of being part of a local/regional/ (inter)national network of ALL's	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	

newly added after validation EAB highlighted by the members of the Pilot Network

Figure 10 Overview of capacity building items after validation by the pilot network

Finally, all mentioned feedback in relation to stakeholder engagement, communication and organisational competencies needed related to living labs will be integrated in the training on setting up and running an agroecology living lab.

A more detailed view of this outcome can also be found as **Annex 7** of this deliverable.

4.5.4 Policy Makers & decision takers

As a last step in the validation process, in February 2022, policy and/or decision makers got the chance of providing feedback about the scoped capacity building program for their target group via a survey developed by the partners of WP5.

In a **short survey** they were asked **about their perspective on the scoped capacity building items**, and they were asked to prioritize their most important item from the proposed list of capacity building items.

These questions were asked for the three levels of the CBP:

- A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agroecology

ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

D5.1 Report on mapped needs and the key end users of the capacity building programme – April 2022

- Living labs and research infrastructures in agroecology
- Agroecology transition in general

The **participant's list** was built up with the help of the SCAR-AE, all the ALL-ready partners, enriching it further on the basis of the EC Funding and tender's website¹⁴ including NCP's related to the field of Agriculture of Member States, Associated countries (*Bosnia & Herzegovina, Iceland, Montenegro, Norway, Serbia, Israel and Turkey*) and Countries in process to association (*UK, Albania, Kosovo*)

The survey was **hosted by the European network of living labs** (ENoLL¹⁵) as lead of the work package 5 on capacity building. They operated as data processor, while the French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the environment (INRAE¹⁶) operated as data controller, in their role as overall coordinator of the ALL-ready project

The survey was **hosted via Surveylegend**¹⁷ and included all necessary privacy measurements to guarantee the privacy of all participants.

In total over 200 policy makers and/or decision makers received an invitation to participate in the survey and state their interest in being involved in the next steps (see 3 Conclusions and next steps)

In total **59** respondents from **23** countries (*Albania, Austria, Belgium, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Luxemburg, Latvia, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Slovenia, United Kingdom, Turkey*) started the survey.

Looking at the level where the participants are active on (43 responses), results show that:

- **13.56 %** of the participants are active on the **regional** level (7 participants)
- **91.52 %** of the participants are active on the **national** level (54 participants)
- **15.25 %** of the participants are active on the **European** level (9 participants)

Some of them are active on multiple levels within Europe.

Analysing the results, **a comparison will be shown between the answers of policy and decision makers from the three different levels.** However, it's important to consider that, due to the low critical mass of regional and European level participants taking part, these **results need to be interpreted carefully to avoid incorrect extrapolations.**

Therefore, the results of this survey provide **solid results for policy and/or decision makers from the national decision levels**, but less accurate results for the other two levels.

The survey also includes **a comparison between the answers of policy and decision makers from 4 European regions:** Northern Europe (n=8), Central/Eastern Europe (n=9), Southern Europe (n=15) and Western Europe (n=27) However, it's important to consider that, due to the low critical mass of Northern and Central/Eastern European participants taking part, these **results need to be interpreted carefully to avoid incorrect extrapolations.**

The first question of the survey was focusing on the **skills and knowledge needed about agroecology in general.**

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/ncp>

¹⁵ <https://www.enoll.org>

¹⁶ <https://www.inrae.fr/en>

¹⁷ <https://www.surveylegend.com/s/3uqf>

Overall, **6.25% indicated none of the proposed formats could improve their skills and knowledge** on this topic.

Missing items indicated by the participants were:

- The relationships between organic farming and agroecology
- Knowledge on measuring trade-offs and comparisons with conventional agriculture
- Linkages on how agroecology can link with all relevant Horizon Europe partnerships but particularly food systems, bioeconomy and digitalisation
- Knowledge on weak spots of agroecology
- Knowledge about how to put agroecology in practice
- A comparison of what agroecology means for the various countries. What are the similarities, and more interestingly what are the differences?
- One size does not fit all, possibilities & solutions of agroecology differ from the south and central European areas.

Summarizing the results from the participants, policy and/or decision makers are **mainly looking for information about agroecology in general** (62.50%) and **knowledge on measuring impacts** of agroecology performances (62.50%). In addition to this more than 6 out of 10 (60.42%) would like to get **access to success stories & best practices in Agroecology**.

They are **less searching for information about policy instruments to support transition to agroecology** (41.67%) and next to this **knowledge on how to foster the multi-stakeholder dialogue about agroecology transition** (43.75%).

Figure 11 Results knowledge and skills agroecology in general policy- and decision makers

Looking at the different levels, shows that *European policy and/or decision makers* are **significantly more** than the other levels **looking for knowledge about agroecology in general** (>15.28%) and **knowledge about fostering dialogue** (>22.92%). In relation to the other two levels is the fact that European policy and/or decision makers are **significantly searching less for knowledge on measuring impacts** (<6.94%).

The **percentages of the regional level** are higher for most proposed formats. However, their interest seems to be very significantly lower when it comes to **knowledge on fostering dialogue about Agroecology transition** (<15.18%)

	Over all	Regional	National	European	Nord	Central & East	South	West
Information about Agroecology in general	62,50	85,71	62,79	77,78	80,00	44,44	60,00	69,57
Information about systems thinking in Agroecology	54,17	71,43	55,81	66,67	80,00	66,67	30,00	56,52
Access to success stories and Agroecology best practices	60,42	71,43	62,79	55,56	60,00	88,89	60,00	52,17
Information about policy instruments for funding resources to support transition to Agroecology (in farms)	54,17	71,43	55,81	66,67	60,00	88,89	30,00	47,83
Information about policy instruments such as regulations to support transition to Agroecology (in farms)	41,67	71,43	41,86	44,44	40,00	55,56	50,00	34,78
Knowledge on measuring impacts about Agroecology performances	62,50	57,14	65,12	55,56	60,00	88,89	30,00	69,57
Knowledge on how to foster dialogue about Agroecology transition	43,75	28,57	48,84	66,67	40,00	100,00	30,00	30,43
None of the above	6,25	0,00	6,98	11,11	0,00	0,00	10,00	8,70

Figure 12 Comparison levels & European regions agroecology in general

Looking at the comparison between the 4 different European regions, it's showing that the proposed skills and knowledge are **significantly higher accepted by Northern Europe**, while **Southern and Western European** policy and/or decision makers are **significantly lower convinced**.

The second question of the survey was focusing on the **skills and knowledge needed about supporting the set-up of agroecology LIs and RIs**.

Overall (all three levels included), **8.51% indicated none of the proposed formats could improve their skills and knowledge** on this topic.

Missing items indicated by the participants were:

- Who are the persons & organisations involved?
- Who are the existing networks dealing with this topic?
- Information in National languages

Summarising the results from the participants, policy and/or decision makers are **mainly looking for information about what RIs infrastructures (70.21%)**, together with **knowledge on how to build skills and competencies (59.57%)** and **access to success stories & best practices of such initiatives (59.57%)**.

All the proposed possibilities are adopted by more than 50% of the participants.

Figure 13 Results agroecology living labs and research infrastructures policy- and decision makers

Comparing the different levels shows that *European policy and/or decision makers* are much **less interested in information about LL & RIs and their benefits** (<24.12%), together with **knowledge on building competencies and skills needed to set-up AE LLS & RIs** (<26.14%). Furthermore, they indicate a **lower need for success stories and best practices** on AE LL & RIs (<15.13%). Finally, more than 1 out of 5 of them indicated None of the above, stating there were missing items in the list (see above).

However, together with the regional level, European policy makers are **looking significantly more for knowledge on policy support for setting up AE LLS & RIs** (>20.33%).

The policy makers at the *regional level*, overall, are clearly indicating they want **more information and knowledge in relation to all proposed topics**.

	ALL	Regional	National	European	Nord	Central/East	South	West
Information about AE LLS & RIs and their benefits	57,45	57,14	58,14	33,33	57,14	77,78	37,50	56,52
Information about what is needed to set up and running AE LLS & RIs	70,21	85,71	69,77	66,67	71,43	88,89	37,50	73,91
Knowledge on how to build competencies & skills within AE LLS & RIs (of different levels, maturity, and geographical scope)	59,57	85,71	58,14	33,33	57,14	100,00	50,00	47,83
Knowledge on policy support for setting up and running AE LLS & RIs	57,45	71,43	58,14	77,78	71,43	77,78	25,00	56,52
Access to success stories & best practices of AE LLS & RIs	59,57	71,43	60,47	44,44	42,86	100,00	37,50	56,52
None of the above	8,51	0,00	9,30	22,22	0,00	0,00	12,50	13,04

Figure 14 Comparison levels & European regions agroecology living labs and research infrastructures

ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

D5.1 Report on mapped needs and the key end users of the capacity building programme – April 2022

Comparing the 4 European regions, **the strong difference between Central & Eastern Europe stands out**, where the Central/Eastern region has a clear higher need than average and the Southern region a significantly lower one compared to the average.

The Northern and Western regions of Europe are mostly in line with the average:

- Northern Europe indicates a higher need for policy support and a lower need for success stories.
- Western Europe indicates a lower need on building competencies

The third question of the survey was focusing on the **skills and knowledge needed to set up a network of AE LLs & RIs**.

Overall (all three levels included), **15.22% indicated none of the proposed formats could improve their skills and knowledge** on this topic.

Missing items indicated by the participants were:

- How to link through to support for CAP strategic plans?
- Linkages with other programs

The policy and/or decision makers are clearly **looking for insights into funding opportunity needs at all levels (65.22%)**, together with **access to best practices of networks of AE LLs & RIs (56.52%)**. Furthermore, they are searching less for **knowledge on measuring impacts about network monitoring (36.96%)**.

Figure 15 Results network of AE living labs & research infrastructures policy- and decision makers

European policy and/or decision makers are significantly **less interested in information about facilitating multi-stakeholder dialogue (<20.65%)**. Furthermore, it stands out that they, score higher than average on most of the other topics. Together with the *regional level* who indicate a higher need for all the proposed topics.

	ALL	Regional	National	European	Nord	Central/East	South	West
Knowledge on policy support for setting up a network of AE LLS & RIs	50,00	71,43	47,62	62,50	42,86	66,67	25,00	54,55
Insights into funding opportunity needs at local, national & European level	65,22	71,43	66,67	87,50	57,14	88,89	25,00	72,73
Information about the promotion and facilitation of multi-actor dialogues in the network	45,65	57,14	47,62	25,00	42,86	66,67	37,50	40,91
Insights into research needs on Agroecology	54,35	71,43	54,76	75,00	71,43	66,67	37,50	50,00
Access to success stories and best practices of networks of (AE) LLS & RIs	56,52	71,43	57,14	62,50	71,43	88,89	37,50	45,45
Knowledge on measuring impacts about long-term sustainability	52,17	71,43	52,38	50,00	57,14	77,78	12,50	54,55
Knowledge on measuring impacts about network monitoring	36,96	71,43	35,71	37,50	42,86	44,44	0,00	45,45
None of the above	15,22	14,29	16,67	0,00	14,29	0,00	37,50	13,64

Figure 16 Comparison levels & European regions network of AE LLS and RIs

Again, looking at the 4 European regions, **big differences between all of them** appear. However, due to the low rate of participants, we need to be careful with extrapolating these results.

Following the validation of the knowledge and the skills needed by policy and/or decision makers. The survey focused on **possible formats** (capacity building items).

Overall (all three levels included), **11.11% indicated none of the proposed formats is fitting their needs**. Following alternatives were proposed by the participants:

- Site/farm visits
- Workshops with actors, EC, member states

The formats perceived as to be most useful by the participants overall are **an online knowledge platform** (57.78%), together with **online training** (53.33%)

The formats perceived as to be the least interesting for the participants are:

- Offline training (28.89%)
- An online (European) community platform (35.56%)
- A permanent discussion forum (35.56%)

Figure 17 results possible capacity building items (formats) policy- and decision makers

The *European level and the regional level* are **significantly looking more for dissemination & promotion events**. On the other side of the spectrum, *both levels* are **less convinced about online training, an online knowledge platform and a permanent discussion forum**.

	ALL	Regional	National	European	Nord	Central/East	South	West
Dissemination & promotion events on Agroecology (online/offline)	46,67	57,14	48,78	75,00	83,33	44,44	25,00	45,45
Online training	53,33	71,43	51,22	50,00	50,00	66,67	37,50	54,55
Offline training	28,89	28,57	31,71	37,50	50,00	44,44	12,50	22,73
An online knowledge platform collecting various information in a central place	57,78	71,43	56,10	50,00	50,00	55,56	37,50	68,18
An online (European) community platform	35,56	42,86	34,15	50,00	33,33	44,44	25,00	36,36
A permanent discussion forum (offline) among policy and/or decision makers (local, regional, national, international)	35,56	14,29	39,02	37,50	33,33	66,67	12,50	31,82
None of the above	11,11	14,29	9,76	0,00	0,00	0,00	37,50	9,09

Figure 18 Comparison levels & European regions possible capacity building items (formats)

The answers from the policy and/or decision makers show once more there are **strong differences between all 4 European regions**.

Based on the previous question (1.4), the next question was only shown to participants (N=20) who indicated online and/or offline training as to be a useful format. The question investigates **the types of training** the participants are looking for.

The **participants ranked the proposed trainings** as follows:

- Agroecological practices, technologies, benefits, impacts economics & finances (82.14%)
- Funding opportunities for setting up a network of AE LLs & RIs (75%)
- Policy support for setting up a network of AE LLs & RIs (75%)
- AE LLs & RIs and their benefits (71.43%)
- Setting up and running AE LLs & RIs (64.29%)
- Promotion and facilitation of multi-actor dialogue (46.43%)

Besides the given options, only **a few additional suggestions** were provided by the participants:

- Not only trainings but physical meetings to discuss interesting processes of living labs
- Practical trainings
- Site visits (e.g. farms)

Figure 19 Results types of training policy- and decision makers

Analysing the different three levels, results in strong deviations, as indicated below. However, as mentioned earlier, we need to consider the lower critical mass regarding provided answers on this question.

It stands out again that there are strong differences between the 4 European regions.

	ALL	Regional	National	European	Nord	Central/East	South	West
Agroecological practices, technologies, benefits, impacts, economics & finances	82,14	100,00	80,00	80,00	100,00	87,50	33,33	84,62
AE LLs & RIs and their benefits	71,43	83,33	72,00	40,00	75,00	75,00	33,33	76,92
Setting up and running AE LLs & RIs	64,29	83,33	64,00	40,00	100,00	75,00	0,00	61,54
Policy support for setting up a network of AE LLs & RIs	75,00	66,67	72,00	80,00	50,00	75,00	100,00	76,92
Funding opportunities for setting-up a network of AE LLs & RIs	75,00	50,00	76,00	80,00	50,00	87,50	33,33	84,62
Promotion & facilitation of multi-actor dialogues	46,43	16,67	52,00	80,00	50,00	62,50	33,33	38,46

Figure 20 Comparison levels & European regions types of training

The last question was only shown to participants (N=19) who indicated in the question on possible formats that an online knowledge platform would be of their interest.

The question investigates **the types of knowledge materials** the participants are looking for.

An overview of agroecological initiatives in the European countries (74.07%), received the highest score from the participants.

While only two proposed type of knowledge material scored less than 50%, namely **methodologies for monitoring impacts of networks** (40.74%) and **methodologies on how to foster dialogue about Agroecology transition** (44.44%)

Type of knowledge material	Percentage %
An overview of existing agroecological initiatives in the European countries	74.07
A clear and shared definition & description about Agroecology in general	70.37
Success stories and best practices	70.37
Recommendations on regulations to support transition in Agroecology	70.37
Methodologies for measuring impacts about Agroecology performances	70.37
Guidelines/implementation plan for setting up a network of AE LLs & RIs	70.37
Recommendations on funding resources to support transition in Agroecology	66.67
A standardized model of Agroecology as a system-based approach	62.96
Guidelines on how to build competencies and skills within AE LLs & RIs	62.96
Methodologies for measuring impacts about long-term sustainability	59.26
Guidelines/recommendations on policy support for setting up and running AE LLs & RIs	59.26
Methodologies on how to foster dialogue between Agroecology transition	44.44
Methodologies for monitoring impacts of networks	40.74

Figure 21 Results types of knowledge materials policy- and decision makers

Comparing the different levels, standing out from the crowd is that participants from the *regional level* have a significantly **lower interest on methodologies for monitoring impacts of networks** (<20.74%) and even less about **methodologies on how to foster dialogue about Agroecology transition** (<24.44%)

European policy makers seem to be **less interested in** knowledge materials about **recommendations about regulations** (<20.37%) and **guidelines on building competencies and skills** (<12.96%)

	ALL	Regional	National	European	Nord	Central/East	South	West
A clear and shared definition 1 description about Agroecology in general	70,37	100,00	66,67	100,00	75,00	40,00	66,67	80,00
A standardized model of Agroecology as a systems-based approach	62,96	100,00	58,33	75,00	75,00	80,00	33,33	60,00
An overview of existing agroecological initiatives in the European countries	74,07	100,00	70,83	100,00	75,00	60,00	33,33	86,67
Success stories and best practices	70,37	80,00	70,83	100,00	75,00	100,00	66,67	60,00
Recommendations on funding resources to support transitions to Agroecology (in farms)	66,67	80,00	66,67	75,00	75,00	80,00	66,67	60,00
Recommendations on regulations to support transition to Agroecology (in farms)	70,37	80,00	70,83	50,00	50,00	100,00	66,67	66,67
Methodologies for measuring impacts about Agroecology performances	70,37	80,00	70,83	75,00	50,00	80,00	66,67	73,33
Methodologies for measuring impacts about long-term sustainability	59,26	80,00	58,33	75,00	50,00	80,00	0,00	66,67
Methodologies for monitoring impacts of networks	40,74	20,00	45,83	50,00	25,00	60,00	0,00	46,67
Methodologies on how to foster dialogue about Agroecology transition	44,44	20,00	50,00	75,00	50,00	60,00	33,33	33,33
Guidelines on how to build competencies and skills within AE LIs & RIs	62,96	80,00	62,50	50,00	50,00	60,00	66,67	66,67
Guidelines and recommendations on policy support for setting up and running AE LIs & RIs	59,26	80,00	58,33	75,00	75,00	80,00	33,33	53,33
Guidelines/implementation plan for setting up a network of AE LIs & RIs (funding schemes, facilitation of multi-actor dialogues...)	70,37	80,00	70,83	75,00	75,00	80,00	66,67	66,67

Figure 22 Comparison levels & European regions types of knowledge materials

Once more we see huge differences between the 4 European regions, but we need to be careful with extrapolation due to the low number of answers from the different regions.

The results of the survey provided valuable insights for the prototyping of the formats (capacity building items) (see 2.3.6) among others for policy makers and/or decision makers. Equally important however, it offered the WP5 partners the opportunity to start arranging these capacity building items in order of importance for this specific group of key end-users, policy- and decision makers.

The results of this survey didn't show the need to further adapt the existing capacity building framework, but they clearly showed additional scoping which is more focused on the 4 European regions is needed. This result will be taken forward during Task 5.2 (Scoping and experimenting).

In **Annex 8** you can find the invitation email as it was sent to the policy and/or decision makers.

In **Annex 9** you can find the full content of the survey as it was sent to the policy and/or decision makers

4.5.5 ALL-Ready consortium meeting March 2022

During the ALL-Ready consortium meeting in Paris in March 2022 two discussion workshops were organised on how to move from the framework towards the next task within WP5, *Task 5.2 Prototyping and experimenting the capacity building programme*.

In these workshops with all WP leads and other project partners, we presented the current 3-layered capacity building framework with all stakeholder groups as potential key end-users for capacity building. We discussed how the output from other WP's contributed to developing insights into key competencies at all levels, needs for competency development across regions and stakeholder groups, and formats for capacity building.

Based on the wide range of this holistic framework, we discussed together with the participants what should be the focus for moving on to the next steps, which are prototyping and experimenting with capacity building items (formats).

Following that discussion, the project partners agreed on the following outcomes to focus on during the prototyping within Task 5.2

Agroecology in general	RECOMMENDATIONS for CB (diversity in stakeholder groups, regional differences and priorities, other CB organisations, etc)
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agroecology	PROTOTYPING AND TESTING: co-creating CBP in ALL-READY (target group is clear, ENOLL expertise in LL, etc)
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agroecology	RECOMMENDATIONS for CB (target group is unknown)

Figure 23 Focus areas within the 3 levels for the prototyping in Task 5.2

Furthermore, it became clear that a glossary with definitions about different aspects of transition to agroecology, setting up LLs & RIs and a network of them is needed to enhance a common understanding within the whole ecosystem of stakeholders related to agroecology and agri-food in general and more specific to agroecology.

Finally, diversifying the CBP based on the 4 European regions makes more sense than a diversification based on the different groups of key end users, since the differences between the groups are smaller than between the different European regions. The project partners agreed on taking these new insights into account during the further prototyping of the CBP (*Task 5.2*), taking advantage of the planned regional workshops within WP3 to further deepen the insights in the different needs of these geographically spread stakeholders.

4.6 Description of validated formats (capacity building items)

Depending on the available resources within the ALL-Ready project, the following formats (Capacity Building items) indicated here below will be further prototyped, experimented with, and implemented, focused on the level of living labs & research infrastructures in agroecology.

Below you can find an overview of all the validated formats for each of the groups of key end-users and each of the levels.

The suggested formats in the tables below are oriented at the individual and institutional level (see 4.1).

- **Agroecology transition in general**

Research	Policy makers	Intermediaries	Farmers	Citizens	Communication
A clear definition & description about agroecology in general compared to other types of farming					

Dissemination & promotion events on Agroecology				A (European) community platform on agroecology	
A standardised model of Agroecology as a system-based approach					
Mapping of the existing agroecological initiatives in the European countries					
Training courses on environmental communication techniques to make agroecology attractive for farmers and consumers	Guidelines on funding resources to support transition	Training on Agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances			
Open databank	KPIs for measuring impacts				
A knowledge catalogue: AE principles, conceptualisation, diversity of transformation, social & economic impacts				A knowledge catalogue	

- **Agroecological living labs & research infrastructures**

Research	Policy makers	Intermediaries	Farmers	Citizens	Communication
Training & education on LLs & lighthouses & RIs and their benefits		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies		Training & education on LLs & lighthouses & RIs and their benefits	
Training on setting up and running AE LLs & RIs					
A knowledge catalogue: roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation	A knowledge catalogue: skills, governance models, business models	A knowledge catalogue: technologies			Transparent way of funding calls & opportunities
Promotion events about AE LLs & RIs	Guidelines on how to build competencies and skills	Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies		Open databank	A (European) community platform on agroecology

- **A European network of Agroecological living labs & research infrastructures**

Research	Policy makers	Intermediaries	Farmers	Citizens	Communication
Mapping of AE LLs & RIs	KPIs for measuring impacts	A (European) community platform on agroecology			
A strategic research agenda about system thinking AE LLs & RIs	Guidelines & training on how to set up a network, facilitate multi-actor dialogue & needed funding schemes	A knowledge catalogue: barriers & benefits of the network, funding & impacts			
Open databank	Living labs/agroecological office	Dissemination & promotion events on Agroecology	Demo videos	Dissemination & promotion events on Agroecology	

5. Conclusions and next steps

The holistic approach taken within *Task 5.1 Scoping the capacity building programme* results into a validated capacity building framework, existing out of three levels:

- Transition to agroecology in general
- Setting up and managing Agroecology Living Labs & Research infrastructures
- Setting up a network of Living Labs & Research Infrastructures

Furthermore, a list of possible formats (capacity building items) has been internally and externally validated by various groups of key-end users.

However, **4 important lessons learned** based on the collected feedback during the validation exercises of the scoping need to be considered in the next phases of the development of the capacity building:

- An **emphasis need to be put in creating a glossary** to enhance common understanding about agroecology in general, but also about living labs, research infrastructures and other related subjects.
- Due to the large amount of possible formats after the scoping process **a prioritisation of the formats (capacity building items) will be needed** to make sure the most important items will be developed within the available budgets of the ALL Ready project. The further prioritization of formats (capacity building items) will happen at the beginning of Task 5.2 Prototyping & experimenting the CBP.
- **More insights need to be collected to diversify the CBP** based on the 4 European sectors (North, South, West, Central & East) instead of focusing on the different groups of key end-users, based on the fact that there are more clear differences from a geographical perspective as from a stakeholder perspective. Collaboration within Task 5.2 with the pilot network in WP3 and the planned regional workshops will be crucial to achieve these insights. Finally insights from the work done within WP2 which are included in deliverable 5.2

Skills and competencies framework, provide a good basis to work on the collection of this data needed.

- Since the target groups of key end-users in the 3 identified levels are not equally clear for all of them (see 2.3.5.4), the prototyping of **the CBP will focus on the level of 'Setting up and managing Agroecology Living labs & research infrastructures'** in collaboration with the pilot network. The two other levels will be approached from a more advisory point of view.

Looking forward to the next steps within work package 5 on capacity building, **the current findings of this deliverable will be used to:**

1. **Prioritise the formats** which will be prototyped (Task 5.2) and implemented (Task 5.3) within the ALL-Ready pilot network (WP3) ;
2. Start the collection of existing knowledge materials to support the prototyping of these items ;
3. **Identify the gaps** between the collected knowledge materials and the concrete needs of the different groups of key end-users, with the help of the pilot network from WP3.

Following these previous 3 steps, the identified formats will be co-created and co-designed (prototyping) together with the pilot network within Task 5.2. Once this task is completed this deliverable will be updated with a more precise description of the capacity building items within section 2.3.6 of this deliverable and/or a new iterated capacity building framework overall will be added based on the new insights collected during Task 5.2

After the prototyping these capacity building items will be implemented in the last year of the ALL-Ready project within Task 5.3

The CBP will be of high benefit to the future partnership since it offers validated insights and formats via WP3 and its pilot network to structure national and European networks of LLs and RIs in the future. In this regard the close collaboration with WP4 on further aligning the capacity building needs with the approach towards the implementation and scaling-up of the network will provide a solid base for future policy makes and decision takers to create these networks in a sustainable way that serves all necessary stakeholders of the agroecology and other food system related ecosystems.

Finally, the developed CBP will also support the further sectoral exploitation of the ENoLL capacity building programme by offering adapted & validated knowledge materials and the identification of experts and trainers

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https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/iscap_e_guidebook_digital (page 79-80, page 124-129)

Organicity Playbook:

http://organicity.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Organicity-Playbook_2018-1.pdf (page 28-29)

United Nations SDG 17:

<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/globalpartnerships/>

United Nations Development group capacity Development:

<https://unsdg.un.org/sites/default/files/UNDG-UNDAF-Companion-Pieces-8-Capacity-Development.pdf>

HLPE report on agroecological and other innovative approaches for sustainable agriculture and food systems:

<https://www.fao.org/3/ca5602en/ca5602en.pdf>

FOA report 10 elements of Agroecology

<https://www.fao.org/documents/card/en/c/I9037EN>

Annex 1: 1st draft of the capacity building programme

	INRAE	Aarhus University	Ömki on farm Living Lab	Thuenen Institute	ENoLL	FiBL Europe	AAFC	EVILVO
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Guidelines for funders. Platforms and events for sharing experiences and competences - Capacity to identify and raise new research questions in the run of LL and RI and to extract the generic value of local advances		To train and support in building the foundation of cooperation among network members (skills needed, capacity needed etc.) and in maintaining this cooperations (clear interest specification)	Capacity and step-by-step guidance to set up, manage and monitor a network and understanding and assessing its long-term sustainability. Guidance for funders and policy stakeholders.	A roadbook for decision makers/officials to set up a network of ALL	1) a guide for policy-makers for understanding all the funding schemes that can support living labs (Research fund, Rural development funds, structural funds, regional funds, social, funds...) including blending opportunities between national and EU funds 2) a guide to facilitate national multi-actor dialogues between national policy-makers and all stakeholders with a stake on Agroecology, LL and RI 3) Tool to facilitate the exchange of best practices at EU level on Agroecology, LL and RI, and the institutional setting to it related		linking and transferring living labs & research infrastructures
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-ecology	- Relative roles of LL and RI - Identify main limits and levers to data management, PI, users involvements - Business models of AE LL and RI; how to value common goods - How to do with imposed time scales (seasonal experimentations) and with long term transformation/impact on future generations - Dealing with very different and		Active to categories of competencies and skills (guideline) on how to build, operate (economic viability) and further innovate within AE LLs and RIs of different levels, maturity and geographic scope	communication and cooperation (facilitating the time-consuming development of trusting relationships between different types of key actors in the ALLs). Roles of research infrastructures and LLs. Integrating ecological / environmental priorities with economic / socio-economic priorities - creating and understanding common objectives. Importance of long term	How to set up a ALL and run it? How to promote agroecology and LL approaches inside RI's	particularities for ALL 2) mapping of EU RI with relevance for agroecology as well as their available data (maybe the VRE or our project mapping) 3) a guide for harmonized data collection for LL and RI to allow exchange and share of data as well as Best Practices 4) practical guide for accessing partnership funding		1) support & initiate living labs & research infrastructures 2) functioning and impact
Agro-Ecology in general	agroecology; - Knowing more about the role of biodiversity; - Share of concept of resilience, robustness, vulnerability - Develop systems and holistic analysis - Innovation tracking and demonstrations - Valorization of agroecological practices and of biodiversity services - Connexion between the farmer and		- Agronomic and practice, technology-related particularities; - holistic view of agroecology; social and economic particularities	Common understanding of the scope and diversity of agroecological transitions including barriers / drivers, benefits and the roles of different types of actors. Understanding longterm implications and benefits of such transitions. Clarifying the relationship between agroecological transitions and organic farming.	What is Agro-ecology? Barriers, impacts, good practices, behavioral change,	1) agroecological practices, definition and scope 2) Best practices sharing and dissemination, including by category of agroecosystem 3) barriers and enablers 4) clear and harmonized categorization of EU agroecosystems to facilitate context-specific strategies of Agroecology deployment		Knowledge on Agro-ecology: barriers & levers
For each level there are 3 'sub-levels' which can be taken into account to further scope & develop the CBP for ALL-ready								
INDIVIDUAL: training programs, business development activities, workshops for in-depth discussion of specific topics; conferences					exchange and ownership			
INSTITUTIONAL: development of internal policies, organizational and procedural restructuring					With the focus on the overall organizational performance and functioning capabilities, as well as the ability of an organization to adapt to change.			
SYSTEMIC: advocacy initiatives, consultations, open dialogue, reforms.					With the emphasis on the overall policy framework in which individuals and organizations operate and interact with the external environment			

Annex 2: Overview what for whom

Stakeholder groups	Research			Farmers			Policy makers			Consumers			Intermediaries (advisers/ training managing Living labs included) & value chain actors			Communication (tools/infrastructure/actions)		
	Input SCAR	Input WPS	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Input WPS	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Input WPS	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Input WPS	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Input WPS	Possible CB items	Input SCAR	Possible CB items	
Agro-Ecology in general	standardized agroecological model for scientific and educational purposes	Conceptualization of transition to agroecology (resilience, robustness, vulnerability)	Standardized agroecological model	Shift from conventional farming	Valorization of agroecological practices & biodiversity services		Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries		Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries	Awareness of the costs and added value of agroecological practices			Incoherence between supporting & hampering transition policies				a specific mechanism to ensure the sharing of experiences and best practices across Member States on the adoption of agroecological approaches	
	methodological approach of agroecological research	Common understanding of the scope and diversity of agroecological transitions including farmers' drivers, benefits and the roles of different types of actors.	Training courses on environmental communication techniques to raise agroecology attractive for farmers & consumers	Absciveness of rural lifestyle & farming	Agronomic and practice	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Long-term, strategic system thinking and planning in agroecological practice	develop systems and holistic analysis	Strategic system thinking agroecological model	realistic expectations in terms of seasonality and types of products you can find			Influence of mainstream farmer organisations on policy processes (lack of support for AE)		Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology			
	long-term data series on agroecosystems + digital and computer models for monitoring	Data collections and sharing	Open databank?	Special attention to aging issue			guides on funding resources to support AE transition farms		Guidelines on funding resources	Affordability of AE products for some groups			retail logistics have been adapted to industrial-scale farming and smaller-scale cannot match				target urban/territorial food movements with communications about AE	A (European) community platform on agroecology (e.g. The facebook for farmers)
	studies on the social and environmental impact of agroecological schemes	social and economic particularities		Knowledge intensity & availability of knowledge to the farmers		A knowledge catalogue	precise indicators that quantify the magnitude & quality of the ecosystem services	innovation tracking and demonstration	KPIs for measuring impacts	challenge to change diets towards 'sustainable diets'			specific long chains may be cheaper to operate than short ones				communication between cities/neighborhoods + between rural areas	
	local knowledge & scattered information	Transversal management	A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts	Lack of education, training, skills on AE	Connection between the farmer & the consumer + the farmer & the citizen	Training an agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances (e.g. "A gro(v) to Z"	Inconsistent, fragmented and uneven structures/mechanisms at the national and European levels to facilitate the co-creation of innovative solutions		Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	difficult logistics access (food deserts where you can only access mainstream food) - less selling gains			Lack of skills and knowledge on AE			A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts	communication between different actors (consumers, research, value chain actors, farmers)	
	agroecological management practices	Understanding long-term implications and benefits of such transitions. Clarifying the relationship between agroecological transitions and organic farming		Labour intensity, AE is more labour intensive, harder to mechanise. Productivity related barriers. Percept of low amenability of production through AE	Technology related particularities		trade off between local empowerment and national commitments						knowledge on how to process AE products (variety or plant mixes)				local knowledge & scattered information	A knowledge catalogue

Annex 2: Overview what for whom

Living labs & research infrastructures in Agroecology	Research laboratories on scientific, technical and socio-cultural and economic agroecological issues	Role and expectations from the local territory	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits	Digital and computer models for farmers including blockchain technologies		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	prepare on farmers & smallholdings to intensify agricultural practices		Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits	research groups for Europe-wide strategies to promote benefits of agroecological schemes to consumers	How to promote agroecology and LL approaches inside RIs	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits	Support peer-learning and co-learning processes/approaches	multi-actor communication & cooperation	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")	leg templates	A (European) community platform		
		Dealing with very different and heterogeneous knowledge (practice and theory, tacit and explicit) - how to value common goods - how to do with imposed time scales (seasonal experimentations) and with long-term	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")		participatory for ALL		skills & knowledge on agroecology	How to set up and run an ALL		Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")		Data sharing & collective	Open databank?	technologies to process AE products		A knowledge catalogue: technologies	a European newsletters service on funding calls and any help for the agroecology sector	Transparent way of funding calls & opportunities	
		Implication of researchers and academics, at which level and for what role	A knowledge catalogue: roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation, best practices, demonstration videos, limits & levers		funding of LL and their set-ups		meta-governance models (large diversity of stakeholders)			A knowledge catalogue: skills, governance models, business models				technologies to manage work farms/shares					
		Integrating ecological / environmental priorities with economic / socio-economic priorities - creating and understanding common objectives			Multi-actor communication and cooperation		business models of AE LL and RI												
		create model regions where demonstration on AE can be made + boosting high tech farming for AE		multi-actor communication & cooperation	Promotion events about ALL's & RIs	Boosting high-tech farming (precision farming, remote control, digital machinery etc.)		Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies			competencies & skills (guidelines) on how to build, create & further improve within AE LL and RIs of different levels, maturity & geographic scope	Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills							

Annex 2: Overview what for whom

A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Living lab covering diversity of territories (riverside labs) and diversity of actors within LL	Capacity to identify and raise new research questions in the sun of LL and RI and to extract the generic value of local advances	Mapping of ALL's & R's	Digital and computer models for farmers including blockchain technologies	ALL-ready-website/knowledge hub	A knowledge catalogue farmers & benefits of networked approach, economical & societal impacts, funding	Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE)	Capacity and step-by-step guidance to set up, manage and monitor a network and understanding and assessing its long-term sustainability. Guidance for funders and policy stakeholders	KPIs for measuring impacts	Platform containing educational products related to capacity building of consumers	ALL-ready-website/knowledge hub	A knowledge catalogue	Support peer learning and co-learning processes/approaches		Online platform where all publications, resources and forums on agroecology are concentrated	A knowledge catalogue
	Meta-analyses		Open databank?	Access to agroecological farm and food system demonstration networks	ALL-ready test network	A (European) community platform	Skills & knowledge development	to train and support in building the foundation of cooperation among network members (skills needed, capacity needed etc.) and in maintaining this cooperation (clear interest, specification)	Guidelines/ roadbook/ training around the set up of a network of ALL		ALL-ready test network		Absence of a specific mechanism to ensure the sharing of experiences		Practical online tool for multi-actors	A (European) community platform
	Banks/repositories of ancient/traditional and minor/organic seeds and varieties		Production of a collection of agroecological farmers stories and testimonies	Tool to facilitate the exchange of best practices at EU level on Agroecology, LL and RI, and the institutional setting to it related	Demonstration videos to show the benefits of being part of a local/regional/ international network of ALL's	A permanent discussion forum among all policy makers (local/regional/ international)	A roadbook for decision makers/officials to set up a network of ALL	facilitate multi-actor dialogues, understand needed funding schemes	Establish research groups for Europe-wide strategies to generate benefits of agroecological schemes to consumers	Tool to facilitate the exchange of best practices at EU level on Agroecology, LL and RI, and the institutional setting to it related	A (European) community platform	Localised/regional knowledge: how to share it?	Developing several local "hubs" rather than centralized forms which can be localized, small "clusters" for sharing knowledge (small distances, similar local characteristics). But the connections between several hubs with a common...	Create a new magazine?	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology
	System thinking as neutral entity point + research strategies as AE management practices		A strategic-system thinking research agenda about ALL's			Living labs/agroecological office	a guide for policymakers for understanding all the funding schemes that can support LLs 2) a guide to facilitate national multi-actor dialogues between national policy-makers and all stakeholders with a stake on Agroecology, LL and RI	Living labs/ agroecological office		LLD01	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Common languages, strategies & communicate between different actors				

Annex 3: Possible formats (capacity building items)

	Research	Policy	Farmers	Consumers	Intermediaries (advisors/ running managing Living labs included) & value chain actors	Communication (tools/infrastructures/actio ns)
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Mapping of ALL's & RI's	KPI's for measuring impacts	A (European) community platform			
	Open databank?	Guidelines/ roadbook/ training around the set up of a network of ALL, facilitate multi-actor dialogues, understand needed funding schemes	A knowledge catalogue: barriers & benefits of networked approach, economical & societal impacts, funding			
	A strategic system thinking research agenda about ALL's	Living labs/ agroecological office	Demonstration videos to show the benefits of being part of a local/regional/ (international network of ALL's	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology		
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-ecology	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		
	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")				Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")	
	A knowledge catalogue: roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation, best practices, demonstration videos, limits & levers	A knowledge catalogue: skills, governance models, business models			A knowledge catalogue: technologies	Transparent way of funding calls & opportunities
	Promotion events about ALL's & RI's	Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills	Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	Open databank?		A (European) community platform
Agro-Ecology in general	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology					A (European) community platform on agroecology (e.g. The facebook for farmers)
	Standardized system thinking agroecological model		Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries			
	Training courses on environmental communication techniques to make agroecology attractive for farmers & consumers	Guidelines on funding resources	Training on agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances (e.g. "A gro(w) to Z")			
	Open databank?	KPI's for measuring impacts				
	A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts		A knowledge catalogue:		A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts	A knowledge catalogue:

Annex 4: Possible formats after input of the external advisory board

	Research	Policy	Farmers	Citizens (consumers, civil society organizations, NGO's...)	Intermediaries (advisors/ running managing Living labs included) & value chain actors (traders, retailers, transport,...)	Communication (tools/infrastructures/actors)
Agro-Ecology in general	A clear definition & description about agroecology in general compared to other types of farming (e.g. organic farming)					
	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology					A (European) community platform on agroecology (e.g. The facebook for farmers)
	Standardized system thinking agroecological model		Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries			
	Training courses on environmental communication techniques to make agroecology attractive for farmers & consumers	Guidelines on funding resources	Training on agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances (e.g. "A gro(w) to Z"			
	Open databank?	KPI's for measuring impacts				
	A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts		A knowledge catalogue:		A knowledge catalogue: conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts	A knowledge catalogue:
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-ecology	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		
	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")				Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")	
	A knowledge catalogue: roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation, best practices, demonstration videos, limits & levers	A knowledge catalogue: skills, governance models, business models			A knowledge catalogue: technologies	Transparent way of funding calls & opportunities
	Promotion events about ALL's & RI's	Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills	Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies	Open databank?		A (European) community platform
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Mapping of ALL's & RI's	KPI's for measuring impacts	A (European) community platform			
	Open databank?	Guidelines/ roadbook/ training around the set up of a network of ALL, facilitate multi-actor dialogues, understand needed funding schemes		A knowledge catalogue: barriers & benefits of networked approach, economical & societal impacts, funding		
	A strategic system thinking research agenda about ALL's	Living labs/ agroecological office	Demonstration videos to show the benefits of being part of a local/regional/ (inter)national network of ALL's	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology		

Annex 5: Competencies to be developed in the LL and RI

What are the main competencies for agroecology transition needed?

Coordinators

- Knowledge
 - Grasp political, ecology/economic perspectives on agroecology
 - How Agroecology Living lab is different from other participatory LL
 - Some in depth knowledge on processes
 - Some agroecology knowledge
 - Knowing your actors/users
 - Understanding of the agroecology sector you work with
 - Understanding and specific experience/knowledge of both research and practical farming skills
 - Networking competencies
 - Ability to quickly build relationships with farmers and other stakeholders
 - Good relationships with funders/sponsors
 - Strong collaborative networks/having useful networks (2)
 - Ability to engage different actors from different backgrounds
 - To be able to bridge between the different actors from various backgrounds and thus different ways of thinking
 - System thinking competencies
 - Whole system perspective/understand
 - Have a systemic approach
 - Communication competencies
 - Sympathetic to other pulls on participants' involvement (farmers or researchers' agenda)
 - Ability to listen more than talking
 - Confidence/knowledge about talking to the media
 - General facilitators skills (2)
 - Understanding of co-design principles and methods
 - Organisational competencies
 - Ability to identify and share key learnings from the living lab
 - Ability to identify key milestones in the living lab
 - Preempting what could go wrong and planning for alternative approaches (incl; funding, time/other resource)
 - Knows the ropes with respect to structuring a living lab
 - Organisation and coordination skills/planning and time management (2)
 - Planning and able to change plans due to things coming up
 - Understand the strategic issues
 - Making a shared goal
 - Guarantee the achievement of the goals defined together
 - Forward thinking and ability to make a synthesis: identify key challenges and opportunities
 - Decision making
 - Report writing
 - Confidence and time to chase data collectors
 - Documentation skills
 - Methodological skills
-
- Leadership & agility competencies
 - Vision

- Have in mind that participants are there for different reasons
- Team player
- Delineation of responsibilities
- Not to be overflowed by contradictory demands
- To be able to bridge the small daily actions to the overall goal of agroecology transition
- Conflict management
- Listening skills/ Active listening
- Positive and constructive mindset
- A mix of people skills and action skills
- To be able to think across disciplines (natural vs. social sciences) or include somebody with these skills
- Business savviness

Other members of the LL/RI

- Knowledge
 - Better understanding of AE principles
 - Practical knowledge about AE
 - Technical experience
 - AE content knowledge
 - Digital competencies (mainly Farmers)
 - Technical and practical knowledge on Agroecology (researchers/farmers/SME's/Advisor)
- Systems thinking (3)
- Communication competencies
 - Collaboration and active listening
 - Communication and collaboration
 - Question asking skills
 - Curiosity and patience (Farmers)
 - Openness
 - Engagement for the network
 - Public speaking (Farmers)
 - Good communication with facilitator to understand responsibilities
 - Holding back on solution before defining problems
- Organisational competencies
 - Innovation management
 - Risk management
 - Experimenting
- Leadership & agility competencies
 - Team player
 - Flexibility
 - Networking skills
 - Willingness to allocate time for a longer period
- Competencies specific for researchers
 - Openness to the other benefits of being involved rather than just the research goal
 - Ability/willingness to conduct "good research" in an environment of change/innovation (Researcher)
 - To recognize opportunities in a living lab to make or take roles (Social Scientists)
 - Willingness to let go of your expectations of the level of robust research that may come out of the living lab

Which competencies needs to be developed?

We want to focus on non-developed competencies in your LL which needs to be upgraded

Coordinators

- Knowledge
 - Improve knowledge on social and economic aspects of agroecology
 - Improve knowledge on involving relevant stakeholders
 - Showcase best practices for different stakeholders (Lifewatch)
 - Skills and best practices to make meetings & updates more efficient (AAFC)
 - Design thinking (do with the unknown)
- Networking competencies
 - Involve all stakeholders in identification, execution, and communication of research (co-creation)
 - Fruitful cooperation with advisors
- System thinking
 - Transdisciplinary (in predominantly nature science contexts)
- Organisational competencies
 - Dealing with complexity (and not getting bogged down in what is complicated) (AAFC)
 - Do more with less!
 - Ability to diversify funding opportunities
 - Business marketing, selling skills
 - Multi-tasking, time management
 - Data management

Other members LL/RI

- Knowledge
 - Facilitation methods (Workshop organizers) AAFC
 - Toolkit of co-creation methods (Workshop organizers) AAFC
 - Training on setting up Living labs (Lifewatch)
 - Training on agroecological transition (Lifewatch)
 - More ecological knowledge & background
 - Political sciences
- Networking competencies
 - Collaboration around skills/methods for monitoring/measurement of carbon sequestration and GHG emissions (AAFC)
- Systems thinking
 - Need to recognize the importance of human/social dimensions of innovation & adoption (AAFC)
- Communication competencies
 - Spread awareness (ILVO)
 - Communicate outside scientific bubble (CropSys)
 - More focus on impact and value creation (CropSys)

Annex 6: Role of the network in capacity building

What can be the role of a network to develop these competencies?

- Knowledge
 - Co-creation & co-design
 - Training
 - Best practices library
 - How to reach not only pioneers, get to know the barriers for the whole population
 - How to reach the ones difficult to reach
 - Methods and skills facilitation
 - Different innovation and knowledge systems
 - different methodologies to bring together multi stakeholders
 - Transfer technical skills and knowledge (e.g., precision agriculture technologies, local sensor, field measurement, plant gas exchange...)
 - Technical skills training (workshops)
 - VRE
 - The network can provide building bricks for capacity building (participatory, agroecology, social...) which can be specified locally

- Networking advantages
 - Events
 - Showcase best practices within the network to motivate actors to join LL across Europe
 - How to deal with these challenges together considering the context
 - information at European level
 - Distributed experiments: key driver of change by testing similar things in different contexts (public policies, consumer preferences, practices)
 - Link with thematic working groups: key drivers
 - Awareness raising to consumers and other actors if the value chain
- The network needs to be achieved on different levels: workgroup, project institutional, topical, organisational...)
- National and regional level makes sense, if it can be done in the future partnership it could work. But the national level would be more logical

What kind of capacity building tools, activities and/or elements would be useful for building these skills and knowledge?

- Best practices very context related
- 1–2-page guides
- Simple videos instead of complicated documents

Annex 7: Possible formats after input of the pilot network members

	Research	Policy	Intermediaries (advisors/ running managing Living labs included) & value chain actors (traders, retailers, transport,...)	Farmers	Citizens (consumers, civil society organizations, NGO's...)	Communication (tools/infrastructures/act ions)
Agro-Ecology in general	A clear definition & description about agroecology in general compared to other types of farming (e.g. organic farming)					
	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology					A (European) community platform on agroecology (e.g. The facebook for farmers)
	Standardized system thinking agroecological model			Mapping of agroecological initiatives in the European countries		
	Training courses on environmental communication techniques to make agroecology attractive for farmers & consumers	Guidelines on funding resources	Training on agroecological benefits, impacts, economics & finances (e.g. "A gro(w) to Z"			
	Open databank ?	KPI's for measuring impacts				
	A knowledge catalogue : AE principles, conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts		A knowledge catalogue : AE principles, conceptualization, diversity of transformation, social & economical impacts			A knowledge catalogue :
Living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-ecology	Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits		Training on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies		Training & education on LL's & lighthouses and their benefits	
	Training on setting up and running an ALL (e.g. "ALL ready to grow?")					
	A knowledge catalogue : roles & expectations, multi-actor cooperation, best practices, demonstration videos, limits & levers	A knowledge catalogue : skills, governance models, business models	A knowledge catalogue : technologies			Transparant way of funding calls & opportunities
	Promotion events about ALL's & RI's	Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills	Demo-events on the use of digital/computer models & farming technologies		Open databank ?	A (European) community platform
A network of living labs & research infrastructures in Agro-Ecology	Mapping of ALL's & RI's	KPI's for measuring impacts	A (European) community platform			
	Open databank ?	Guidelines/ roadbook/ training around the set up of a network of ALL, facilitate multi-actor dialogues, understand needed funding schemes	A knowledge catalogue : barriers & benefits of networked approach, economical & societal impacts, funding			
	A strategic system thinking research agenda about ALL's	Living labs/ agroecological office	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	Demonstration videos to show the benefits of being part of a local/regional/ (inter)national network of ALL's	Dissemination & Promotion events on Agroecology	

newly added after validation EAB
highlighted by the members of the Pilot Network

Annex 8: Invitation for policy makers

Dear Mr./Mrs.

At this moment the European Commission is drafting the proposal for a European Partnership under Horizon Europe for Accelerating farming systems transition by agroecology Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs).

Linked to this future proposal two European Coordination and Support Action (CSA)-projects are running to prepare this partnership: [ALL-Ready](#) and [AE4EU](#) which work closely together with the SCAR Strategic Working group on Agroecology in further preparing the future partnership.

Within the context of ALL-Ready a Capacity Building Programme (CBP) is being scoped that will support the further development, and exchange between existing and new LLs and RIs. The CBP will focus on 3 different levels concerning Agroecology:

- Agroecology in general,
- Living Labs and Research Infrastructures in Agroecology
- A network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures.

Looking at these levels a variety of training activities will be developed to address all the needs from different stakeholders. Various materials like an online knowledge library, e-courses, webinars, roadmaps, guidebooks, policy briefs, awareness exhibition, etc. will be developed or collected.

As a policy maker and/or decision maker, you can play a crucial role in developing the Capacity Building Programme. Therefore, we would like to have your input to scope the capacity building programme for policy makers and/or decision makers as well.

We kindly invite you to spend 5 minutes of your time to provide feedback to us on the Capacity Building Programme for supporting the creation of a network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures.

Finally, **feel free to forward this invitation** to any policy maker and/or decision maker you think might benefit from participating in it.

Thank you so much for completing our small survey here: <https://www.surveylegend.com/s/3uqf>

Annex 9: Survey for policy makers

Welcome,

In this short survey, we invite you to answer a couple of questions to scope the Capacity Building Programme for policy makers developed within the [ALL-Ready](#) project to make sure it fits your needs as a policy maker and/or decision maker.

You as policy maker are crucial in empowering transition towards agroecology, in supporting the foundation of Agroecology Living Labs and/or Research Infrastructures and setting up a network of Agroecology LLs and RIs on a European level.

Thank you for your precious time.

The ALL-Ready Consortium is committed to protect your personal data and to respect your privacy. **Personal data are collected and further processed in compliance with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016** on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR).

The ALL-Ready project aims to prepare a framework for a future European network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. The project is conducted by a Consortium of 13 partners (including three which are based in non-EU countries but legally committed to comply with the GDPR principles).

You are invited to participate in an ALL-Ready activity by completing **the short survey "Capacity Building programme for policy makers"** which **is conducted by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)** as the Consortium member responsible for Capacity building.

The results of this survey will be used to validate the scope of the capacity building programme.

Your participation will take approximately 5 minutes and is voluntary. You may choose not to participate or to withdraw at any time, without being penalised.

On the legal ground of consent, personal information considered as strictly necessary to reach the survey goal will be collected by ENoLL and processed by the Consortium members working on related tasks using password-protected tools. They will not be shared publicly.

Contact information:

If you have comments, questions or concerns, or if you would like to submit a complaint regarding the collection and use of your personal data, please feel free to contact:

- The data processor: ENoLL, koen.vervoort@enoll.org
- The data controller: French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), ALL-Ready Coordinator: heather.mckhann@inrae.fr / ophelie.bonnet@inrae.fr

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Do you agree with the statement above?

- Yes
- No

(If no is answered participants are redirected to the last page of the survey where they are asked if they want to be kept up to date)

As a policy maker and/or decision maker, you act at:

Multiple answers are possible

- Regional level
- National level
- European level
- Other, namely :

What would help you to improve your skills and/or knowledge as a policy maker and/or decision maker to **empower agroecology in general?**

Multiple answers are possible.

- Information **about Agroecology** in general
- Information about **systems thinking** in Agroecology
- Access to **success stories and Agroecology best practices**
- Information about policy instruments for **funding resources** to support transition to Agroecology (in farms)
- Information about policy instruments such as **regulations** to support transition to Agroecology (in farms)
- Knowledge on **measuring impacts** about Agroecology performances
- Knowledge on how to **foster dialogue about Agroecology** transition
- None of the above

In your opinion, **what is missing** on the list above to improve your skills and/or knowledge as a policy maker and/or decision maker to **empower agroecology in general?**

What would help you to improve your skills and/or knowledge as a policy maker and/or decision maker to **support the foundation of Agroecology (AE) Living Labs (LLs) and/or Research infrastructures (RIs) in your country or region?**

Multiple answers are possible.

- Information about **AE LLs & RIs and their benefits**
- Information about **what is needed** to set up and running AE LLs & RIs
- Knowledge on **how to build competencies & skills** within AE LLs & RIs (of different levels, maturity, and geographical scope)
- Knowledge on **policy support** for setting up and running LLs & RIs
- Access to **success stories & best practices** of AE LLs & RIs
- None of the above

In your opinion, **what is missing** on the list above to improve your skills and/or knowledge as a policy maker and/or decision maker to **support the foundation of Agroecology (AE) Living Labs (LLs) and/or Research Infrastructures (RIs) in your country or region?**

What would help you to improve your skills and/or knowledge as a policy maker and/or decision maker to **set up a European network of Agroecology (AE) Living Labs (LLs) and/or Research Infrastructures (RIs)?**

Multiple answers are possible.

- Knowledge on policy **support** for setting-up a network of AE LLs & RIs
- Insights into **funding opportunity needs** at local, national & European level
- Information about the **promotion and facilitation of multi-actor dialogues** in the network
- Insights into **research needs on Agroecology**
- Access to **success stories & best practices** of networks of (AE) LLs & RIs
- Knowledge on measuring impacts about **long-term sustainability**
- Knowledge on measuring impacts about **network monitoring**
- None of the above

In your opinion, **what is missing** on the list above to improve your skills and/or knowledge as a policy maker and/or decision maker to **set up a European network of Agroecology (AE) Living Labs (LLs) and/or Research Infrastructures (RIs)?**

From your perspective what would be good **instruments** (formats) to help you improve your skills and knowledge as a policy maker and/or decision maker?

Multiple answers are possible.

- Dissemination & promotion **events** on Agroecology (online/offline)
- **Online training**
- **Offline training**
- An **online knowledge platform** collecting various information in a central place
- An **online (European) community platform**
- A **permanent discussion forum (offline) among policy makers** (local, regional, national, international)
- None of the above

In your opinion, **what instruments are missing** on the list above to improve your skills and/or knowledge as a policy maker and/or decision maker?

What kind of training would you be looking for?

(only showed to who marked online and/or offline training in the question on the previous page)

- Agroecological practices, technologies, benefits, impacts, economics & finances

- AE LLs & RIs & their benefits
- Setting up and running AE LLs & RIs
- Policy support for setting up a network of AE LLs & RIs
- Funding opportunities for setting-up a network of AE LLs & RIs
- Promotion and facilitation of multi-actor dialogues
- Other, namely:

What kind of knowledge materials would you want to find on the online knowledge platform?

Multiple answers are possible.

(Only showed to who marked knowledge platform in the question on the previous page)

- A clear and shared definition & description about Agroecology in general
- A standardized model of Agroecology as a systems-based approach
- An overview of existing agroecological initiatives in the European countries
- Success stories & best practices
- Recommendations on funding resources to support transition to Agroecology (in farms)
- Recommendations on regulations to support transition to Agroecology (in farms)
- Methodologies for measuring impacts about Agroecology performances
- Methodologies for measuring impacts about long-term sustainability
- Methodologies for monitoring impacts of networks
- Methodologies on how to foster dialogue about Agroecology transition
- Guidelines on how to build competencies & skills within AE LLs & RIs (of different levels, maturity, and geographical scope)
- Guidelines and recommendations on policy support for setting up and running LLs & RIs
- Guidelines/implementation plan for setting up a network of AE LLs & RIs (funding schemes, facilitation of multi-actor dialogues...)
- Other, namely:

If you want to be kept up to date concerning the developed capacity building items within the ALL-Ready project and/or want to actively participate in the prototyping of these capacity building items, feel free to indicate as such here below.

If so, we kindly ask you to leave behind your email address to allow us to contact you.

This email address will only be used to contact you about updates of the capacity building program and/or to invite you to participate in future activities in the context of the ALL-Ready project

- Yes, please keep me up to date about future developments of the Capacity Building program of ALL-Ready
- Yes, I want to actively participate in the further development of capacity building items within the context of the ALL-Ready project
- No, I'm not interested in the previous choices

My e-mail address to contact me is:

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